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Using Graph Data Structures for Event Logs

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1 Introduction

Process mining as described in by Wil van der Aalst in [1] is a combination of data mining and business process management to a new discipline. The general purpose of process mining is to derive process insights from event data captured by information systems in the form of an event log. Three main applications of process mining are process discovery, process enhancement and process conformance checking. However, all techniques of these applications rely on event logs at some point. Event logs form the base of most techniques and are oftentimes created from multiple sources that are involved in the process that is subject to the research. Today, event logs usually consist of a table where every row represents a single event with activity name, case identifier, timestamp and optionally event attributes and case attributes. Event logs usually come in .csv or .xes format and reach from basic (activity, case id, timestamp) to extensive forms with different attributes for various activities and cases enriched with workflow lifecycle data. These event logs in table format can be queried with SQL, but interesting queries in the process context like "cases where activity A is followed by activity B" cannot be formulated. This form of storing data is not considered optimal since it does not implement the second normal form used in database normalization, nor does it generally allow for direct application of basic process mining techniques like the creation of a directly follows graph of activities while retaining the specific event data. This report explores graph data structures as alternative format to store event logs as base for process mining. These graph-based event logs are henceforth referred to as graph event logs.

The main contribution of this report is to address and answer the following research questions:

1. How can the concepts of event logs be represented in graph databases?
2. How to use graph-based queries to answer process analysis questions within and across cases?

<https://www.overleaf.com/project/5be95b119f0dd86be9c4bfb4> Research question 1 can be broken down into two sub-questions:

- 1.a How can cases and the temporal and causal ordering of events be represented in graphs?
- 1.b How can attributes and values be stored and shared across cases?

In chapter 2 we provide preliminary information about event logs for process mining and property graph data structures. Chapter 3 introduces the case study, i.e. BPI Challenge 2017 (BPIC17)¹ dataset, and the methods used for this research assignment. The transition from the sequential event log to a graph event log based on the case study is described in chapter 4. Chapter 5 is dedicated to querying a graph event log to evaluate our approach. In chapter 6 we draw the conclusions of this research assignment and give an outlook on how the graph-based representation of event data and queries could be used in the future of process mining.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.4121/uuid:5f3067df-f10b-45da-b98b-86ae4c7a310b>

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Event Log

The notion of event logs used for this report is based on [1]. In event logs for process mining we assume that a log contains the events of a single process with case identifiers and activities as minimum required elements of the log such that the combination of activity and case represent an event. In other words, a case in the event log represents a process instance and an activity refers to a task within a process instance. Table 2.1 shows a basic example of an event log. Every row represents an event in an application process for loans. *A_Create Application* is the first activity of case *430577010*, which consists of 7 events in total. The "time" column adds information about the timing of the events. In the example in table 2.1 we have the timestamp on task completion, other event logs may contain additional timestamps e.g. for the start of a task allowing to generate more insights on the respective activities like throughput times. However, timestamps don't belong to the set of minimum required elements since we generally assume that the events are grouped by case and the order of activities in the log corresponds to the temporal order in which they have been observed in the system. The sequence of activities within a case is called a trace. The example log has 2 trace variants, because cases *430577010* and *1639247005* have an identical sequence of activities while the sequence of activities in case *180427873* is different. A log can contain any number of columns. In our example log we have 3 more columns, "resource", "amount" and "offer". These columns are called attributes. In general we differentiate between event attributes and case attributes. The "resource" column represents the user that generated the event and probably also executed the respective activity which is a typical event attribute that can be found in many event logs. The "amount" column provides the loan value that has been applied for in the loan application and thus represents a case attribute. The information that this is a case attribute is not explicitly contained in the .csv table and has been derived from the fact that this value does not change throughout all events of a case in the log. Not every event needs to have the same set of attributes. This becomes clear when we inspect the "offer" column. It belongs to the event attribute category, since *O_Create Offer* of case *430577010* has the offer id *104557954* and the offer id is only used for certain activities. There can also be more than one offer like in case *180427873*, indicating that an offer should rather be treated as a separate object or entity of the process which might also have its own attributes contained in the log. In sequential event logs information about such process specific entities and their affiliated attributes is only contained implicitly. We use the notion of an entity to describe process related objects that have no predefined standard notion in event logs. An entity of a process can be any object or concept with distinct existence related to the process, e.g. an invoice, an offer or a workflow.

Event logs can, for example, be used to discover process models as described in chapters 6 and 7 of [1] or compared with a reference model to determine whether log and model fit as profoundly discussed in [2]. Depending on how much information is contained in the event log further information on the process can be derived, such as hand-over of work relationships of resources or the general process performance. Please refer to chapter 9 of [1] for further information on these process mining perspectives.

2.2 Graph Database

Generally, a graph is a collection of vertices and edges. In the context of graph databases (DB), vertices are often referred to as nodes and edges as relationships. Graphs can be represented in a database in different ways like hypergraphs, property graphs or triples. The database management system (DBMS) we used for this research assignment makes use of a specific type of property graph, thus we introduce the concept of graph databases with the help of a labeled property graph, which has the following characteristics [3]:

case	activity	time	resource	amount	offer
430577010	A_Create Application	17.03.2016 17:32:13	User_24	5000	
430577010	O_Create Offer	17.03.2016 19:19:42	User_24	5000	104557954
430577010	O_Created	17.03.2016 19:19:43	User_24	5000	104557954
430577010	O_Sent (mail and online)	17.03.2016 19:21:56	User_24	5000	104557954
430577010	A_Incomplete	23.03.2016 17:02:03	User_101	5000	
430577010	O_Accepted	24.03.2016 10:11:02	User_116	5000	104557954
430577010	A_Pending	24.03.2016 10:11:02	User_116	5000	
1639247005	A_Create Application	22.04.2016 12:40:22	User_61	10000	
1639247005	O_Create Offer	22.04.2016 16:40:37	User_61	10000	110013904
1639247005	O_Created	22.04.2016 16:40:38	User_61	10000	110013904
1639247005	O_Sent (mail and online)	22.04.2016 16:41:30	User_61	10000	110013904
1639247005	A_Incomplete	23.04.2016 10:33:30	User_61	10000	
1639247005	O_Accepted	29.04.2016 16:08:15	User_90	10000	110013904
1639247005	A_Pending	29.04.2016 16:08:15	User_90	10000	
180427873	A_Create Application	06.09.2016 10:21:43	User_56	26000	
180427873	O_Create Offer	06.09.2016 11:29:39	User_56	26000	1156783066
180427873	O_Created	06.09.2016 11:29:39	User_56	26000	1156783066
180427873	O_Create Offer	06.09.2016 11:45:21	User_56	26000	1156783067
180427873	O_Created	06.09.2016 11:45:21	User_56	26000	1156783067
180427873	A_Cancelled	07.10.2016 8:00:17	User_1	26000	
180427873	O_Cancelled	07.10.2016 8:00:17	User_1	26000	1156783066
180427873	O_Cancelled	07.10.2016 8:00:17	User_1	26000	1156783067

Table 2.1: Event Log Example

- A graph consists of nodes and relationships
- Each node and relationship can have an arbitrary number of properties in the form of key-value pairs
- A node can have one or multiple labels
- A relationship always has a start and end node and thus is directed
- Every relationship has a name

We want to illustrate these characteristics with the help of relationships between a paper and its authors shown in figure 2.1. The circles are the nodes and the arrows are the edges. The example contains nodes with different labels, i.e. *:Person*, *:Professor*, *:Student* and *:Document*. The labels enable us to group nodes with the same label. The coloring in figure 2.1 is to illustrate that *Dirk* and *Stefan* belong to the group of nodes with the label *:Person* and the *Paper* has no label in common with other nodes. By referring to nodes as *Dirk* or *Stefan* we already introduced the next characteristic in our example, namely properties. In the example all nodes with the *:Person* label have a property called name and the *:Document* has a type. However, the visualization of graph structures often require some abstraction in order to keep it readable, because the properties of the nodes are not limited to what is shown. The *Paper* node, for example, could have other properties like title or abstract and a *:Person* node could have an address property. The same applies to the properties of relationships, since *Dirk* *:SUPERVISES* *Stefan* as of 02.09.2018 and the relationship might get a property *end_date* as soon as this report is finished. Nodes with the same label do not necessarily need to have the same set of properties, but from a data modeling perspective it is useful ensure some form of consistency such that nodes with the same label also have the same attributes defined.

Figure 2.1: Example Graph Illustration

While figure 2.1 illustrates a specific set of nodes and relationships, it does not give us the complete picture of the data structure. Including every detail would heavily reduce the readability when the set of labels, nodes, properties and relationships grows. For this representation, we opt for a table format. This requires one table for the nodes and one for the relationships. For our example this might look as follows:

Label	Properties
:Person	Name* Address
:Professor	EmployeeID* Department Group
:Student	StudentID* Program
:Document	Title* Type Abstract

Table 2.2: Example Graph Nodes Table

Note that the properties marked with an asterisk* in table 2.2 might serve as unique identifier for a node. However, when storing this structure in a DBMS there might also be some internal unique identifier, hence a specification of a unique id is not required.

Relationships need a source and a destination node. Name and direction of a relationship corresponds to the type of a relationship. Generally, the type does not limit a relationship to originate from or end at nodes with predefined labels. However, to develop a meaningful schema for the graph database we want to specify between which type of nodes (labels) what type of relationship (name) can be established. Table 2.3 shows the relations of our example.

As we can see in table 2.3, relationships are not required to have properties. The same applies to nodes. With figure 2.1, table 2.2 and table 2.3 we showed exemplary how a labeled property graph structure can be represented. The fact that relations between individual data points and the data points themselves are equally important in graph databases allows to create many different views on the same data in a more flexible way than we are used to from relational databases.

Start Node Label	Name	End Node Label	Properties
:Professor	:SUPERVISES	:Student	start_date end_date
:Person	:IS_AUTHOR_OF	:Document	
:Person	:IS_COAUTHOR_OF	:Document	

Table 2.3: Example Graph Relationships Table

2.3 Cypher

"Cypher is a declarative query language for property graphs. Cypher provides capabilities for both querying and modifying data, as well as specifying schema definitions." [4]. In the following paragraphs we introduce all relevant aspects of Cypher w.r.t. this paper.

2.3.1 Nodes and Relationships

Cypher recognizes nodes as round brackets "()". Where the empty node "" represents a wildcard for any node label. To narrow the selection of nodes down, Cypher provides different options. "(:Person)" limits the results to the nodes with the label *:Person* and "(:Person {Name: 'Stefan'})" takes a property into account and will take only the nodes with label *:Person* and name *Stefan*. Selection of nodes based on properties without specifying a label is also possible. The notion of nodes may take multiple labels as well as multiple properties into account that can be generally represented as "(:Label_1, :Label_2, ..., :Label_n {Property_1: '#Value_1', Property_2: '#Value_2', ..., Property_n: '#Value_n'})". If we need the resulting nodes for later clauses, we can add a variable name before the first colon "(p:Person {Name: 'Stefan'})". "p" could then be used to refer to all nodes with label *:Person* and name *Stefan*. If we want to assign all nodes to a variable, regardless of their properties or labels, we can use the node wildcard "" with a variable name "n" to get "(n)".

Relationships are represented by dashes. "--" is the undirected wildcard and "<--" or "-->" are directed wildcards. As mentioned earlier, a relationship requires a start and an end node in a labeled property graph. Thus, the minimum required elements to represent a relationship are two nodes and one relationship "()-()-()". This pattern matches all relationships without any restrictions in their properties, labels, directions or start and end nodes. Similarly to nodes, we can make the selection criteria for relationships more strict in terms of direction "()->()", relationship name "()-[:SUPERVISES]->()", properties "()-[start_date: '02-09-2018']->()" or properties and relationship name "()-[:SUPERVISES {start_date: '02-09-2018'}]->()". Note that for relationships only one name exists, which defines the type of the relationship and their number of properties can be zero or many. Relationships can also be stored in variables in a similar way like nodes: "()-[r:SUPERVISES]->()" and assigning a whole path to a variable can for example be done by "p = (:Person)-->(:Person)-[:IS_AUTHOR_OF]->(:Document)".

2.3.2 Clauses

Cypher implements a large set of clauses. This section introduces the subset of clauses that have been used for this research based on the Neo4j Cypher Manual [5] and on the paper by Francis et al. [4].

MATCH

"MATCH" specifies the patterns to be searched for in the database. It is the matching command that has implicitly been used to introduce the node and relationship representation in section 2.3.1. The "MATCH" clause can be aliased with the "AS".

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor) -[:SUPERVISES] ->(:Person {Name: 'Stefan'}) AS  
SupervisorsToStefans
```

This line will match any node that has a `:SUPERVISES` relationship to a `:Person` with the name `Stefan`. The resulting set of patterns can be referred to as "SupervisorsToStefans" and the matched `:Professor` nodes can be referred to as "(p)" in consecutive clauses. However, the "MATCH" clause alone will not return or manipulate any data. It only matches patterns.

RETURN

"MATCH" followed by a "RETURN" clause is one of the most basic queries in Cypher. "RETURN" receives the set of patterns matched by "MATCH".

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor) -[:SUPERVISES] ->(:Person {Name: 'Stefan'})  
2 RETURN (p)
```

The query above will return all `:Professor` nodes as variable "(p)". This result may contain duplicates. In our example, `Dirk` would be included twice if he supervised a second `:Student` with name `Stefan`. If this is not desired, "DISTINCT" can be added to the "RETURN" clause.

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor) -[:SUPERVISES] ->(:Person {Name: 'Stefan'})  
2 RETURN DISTINCT (p)
```

Now `Dirk` will only be returned once, regardless of the number of matched patterns `Dirk` is included.

WITH

The "WITH" clause can manipulate the results from its preceding clause before it hands it to the succeeding clause. Thus, "WITH" is always located between two other clauses.

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor) -[r:SUPERVISES] ->(:Person {Name: 'Stefan'})  
2 WITH COUNT(r) AS NoOfSupervisions, (p)  
3 RETURN (p), NoOfSupervisions
```

The `COUNT()` function aggregates the matched "-[r:SUPERVISES]->" relationships per "(p)" providing the count of the aggregated relationships. Cypher offers an extensive set of predefined functions and also allows the definition of user-defined queries. Please note that the example query above serves the purpose of illustrating the use of "WITH". The exact same result can also be produced by using the following query:

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor) -[r:SUPERVISES] ->(:Person {Name: 'Stefan'})  
2 RETURN (p), COUNT(r) AS NoOfSupervisions
```

Both queries count the number of `:SUPERVISES` relationships with respect to (p) and set the alias "NoOfSupervisions" to the result. The difference between the two queries is the data handed over to the "RETURN" statement. While the latter query can make use of the "r" variable, i.e. the individual `:SUPERVISES` relationships in the patterns delivered by the "MATCH" clause, the first query's "WHERE" only has the aggregated count available.

WHERE

"WHERE" is a sub-clause of reading clauses ("MATCH" and "WITH"). It is used to put constraints to the patterns matched by "MATCH" or to filter the results of a "WITH" clause. Note that the effect of "WHERE" depends on the preceding reading clause. "WHERE" following "MATCH" constrains every single pattern while matching, i.e. only patterns that conform to the "WHERE" are matched. When

using "WHERE" after "WITH", the "WHERE" clause filters from the whole set of patterns, i.e. the patterns get matched according to the "MATCH" clause and then filtered by "WHERE".

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor)-[r:SUPERVISES]->(Person {Name: 'Stefan'})
2 WITH COUNT(r) AS NoOfSupervisions, (p)
3 WHERE NoOfSupervisions > 1
4 RETURN (p)
```

Suppose the data structure of our example in section 2.1 does not allow for more than one *SUPERVISES* relationship between a *Student* and a *Professor*. Then, the statement above will return all *Professor* nodes that supervise more than one different Stefan. If the data structure would allow multiple *SUPERVISES* relationships between two individual nodes, say for every supervised *Document* one to enrich them with document specific properties, then the statement would return all *Professor* nodes that supervise the creation of at least two documents of any *Stefan*, which is possibly but not necessarily the same person.

ORDER BY

"ORDER BY" is another sub-clause. It can be used following "RETURN" or "WITH" and, as its name suggests, orders the output of the respective clause.

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor)-[r:SUPERVISES]->(Person {Name: 'Stefan'})
2 RETURN (p), COUNT(r) AS NoOfSupervisions
3 ORDER BY NoOfSupervisions DESC
```

By default the output is in ascending order, by adding "DESC[ENDING]" after the variable to sort on the order can be reversed. The above query will return the professors supervising a *Stefan* and the respective number of supervisions in descending order.

LIMIT

"LIMIT" constraints the number of output rows.

```
1 MATCH (p:Professor)-[r:SUPERVISES]->(Person {Name: 'Stefan'})
2 RETURN (p), COUNT(r) AS NoOfSupervisions
3 ORDER BY NoOfSupervisions DESC
4 LIMIT 1
```

The above query limits the output to one. The output will be one of the professors with the most supervisions in the matched patterns.

CREATE

With "CREATE" nodes, relationships and complete paths can be created by using their respective representations introduced in section 2.3.1.

The following statement creates a single node with two labels and the name *Miro*:

```
1 CREATE (:Student:Person {Name: 'Miro'})
```

The newly created node *Miro* is yet disconnected from the other nodes as shown in figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Example Graph Illustration with new Node (disconnected)

The following statement exemplifies the creation of the relationship between *Dirk* and *Miro* when both nodes already exist in the graph, i.e. only the relationship is created. Resulting in the graph illustrated in figure 2.3.

```

1 MATCH (p: Professor {Name: 'Dirk'}), (s: Student: Person {Name: 'Miro'})
2 CREATE (p) -[:SUPERVISES]->(s)

```


Figure 2.3: Example Graph Illustration with new Node (connected)

If we desire to create a node and a relationship between an existing and that new node in one go, we can use a different approach. The next statement directly creates a *:SUPERVISES* relationship between the existing *:Professor* node named *Dirk* and the new node *Miro*. Note that this query will create a new node for *Miro*, regardless if a similar node already exists because *Miro* has not been included from the "MATCH" clause.

```

1 MATCH (p: Professor {Name: 'Dirk'})
2 CREATE (p) -[:SUPERVISES]->( : Student: Person {Name: 'Miro'})

```

Suppose this query has been performed on the graph in figure 2.1. The resulting graph will have the structure shown in figure 2.3.

MERGE

Simply said, "MERGE" can be seen as a combination of "MATCH" and "CREATE". It ensures the existence of the pattern specified in the clause. Consider the graph shown in figure 2.2 as starting point and we want to have a :SUPERVISES relationship between *Dirk* and all students in our graph, but only if such a relationship does not exist already.

```
1 MATCH (d:Professor:Person {Name: "Dirk"}) ,(s:Student)
2 MERGE (d) -[:SUPERVISES]->(s)
```

Because the specified pattern in the "MERGE" clause already exists for *Dirk* and *Stefan*, no new relationship is created for that match. Only *Dirk* and *Miro* are connected with a new relationship resulting in the graph shown in figure 2.3.

LOAD CSV

"LOAD CSV" is used to import csv files. The clause can be used with various parameters to cope with the different variants of csv files. The "LOAD CSV" clause needs a variable specified with "AS", similar to the aliases introduced earlier. Similar to the "MATCH" clause with a variable, the aliased variable contains the set of matched patterns which are all rows from the csv file in this case. To work with specific columns one can specify this by column index "variable[index]" or, if the csv contains column headers, by column name "variable[columnName]".

2.4 Neo4j

Neo4j is the graph DBMS used for this research. Neo4j, Inc. describes its product as an ACID compliant DBMS with highly performant read and write scalability that relies on a native graph storage [6]. Cypher has its roots at Neo4j [4]. Neo4j Desktop is suitable to install a local database and comes with Neo4j Browser, a console tool that enables the user to run queries on a database and inspect results with a basic visualization.

3 Methods

In this chapter we present our approach to explore how to represent and access event log information in a property graph. We combine the concepts of event logs and property graphs introduced in section 2 to learn how, for example, the temporal ordering of events or their affiliation with a specific case can be represented as a set of nodes and relationships with properties and labels.

In section 3.1 we provide an overview of our approach. Section 3.2 describes the data set we used as case study for this research and in section 3.3 we define a set of insights we want to get from the data of our case study. These insights are aligned to the event log concepts and form the base for the graph data model for the log.

3.1 Approach

We used the BPIC17 as case study to conduct our research. The log contains, next to the events directly related to the main process instance, additional workflow information and events that are related to a sub process for offers. The aim of this research is to explore the feasibility of using graph databases to store event logs for process mining. Property graphs allow to flexibly model your data and thus design decisions need to be taken, e.g. a column in an event log table might become a property of a node type or a node type itself. Yet, no schema or guideline exists how to transform a sequential event log into a property graph representation. Therefore, we base our design decisions on the information we want to retrieve from the respective case study data set. Thus we first define a set of typical insights we want to get from the log and create the graph model based on these insights. To create the graph based log and access the information from the graph we use Cypher as query language and resort to the query concepts introduced in 2.3.2. Besides some data preparation steps, such as adding indices for sequences to the events of identified process entities to the event log table, we solely use Cypher queries to create the graph and access its information. We use Neo4j as DBMS for the implementation.

To verify that the information of the log is still contained in the graph event log, a fixed subset of 20 cases of the BPIC17 will be transferred to the new graph structure and queried with Cypher to generate the previously defined insights and the results are compared with results from traditional process mining tools like ProM or Disco used with the original event log.

3.2 Dataset

BPIC17 is an event log of a loan application process of a Dutch financial institute. It consists of 561761 events from 31509 cases.

The trivially identifiable elements of the log are case identifier, activity name and the timestamps. For the other columns, domain knowledge and the presence or absence of a value in a certain column can help to determine whether a column can be affiliated with a case, an event or even with some other entity of the process. However, in general case identifier and activity name can be freely chosen among the attributes. This enables process discovery techniques to generate different perspectives of the process while keeping the same event log structure. For our case study we choose the case identifier "case" and activity name "event" by interpreting the column naming and the respective cell values. Table 3.1 gives an overview how assigned we matched the event log characteristics to the columns of the case study log.

The identification of timestamps in this data set has been rather trivial. We have a "startTime" and a "completeTime" column indicating the start and end of an activity. For the decision whether a column should be declared an event attribute or a case attribute, we had to take a closer look at the data as we did for the case identifier and the activity name. To classify a column as a case attribute, a column must

#	Column name	Data type	Event log element
1	case	String	<i>Case identifier</i>
2	event	String	<i>Activity name</i>
3	startTime	Datetime	<i>Event timestamp</i>
4	completeTime	Datetime	<i>Event timestamp</i>
5	LoanGoal	Integer	Case attribute
6	ApplicationType	Integer	Case attribute
7	RequestedAmount	Float	Case attribute
8	Accepted	Boolean	Case attribute
9	Action	String	Event attribute
10	FirstWithdrawalAmount	Float	Event attribute
11	NumberOfTerms	Integer	Event attribute
12	OfferID	String	Event attribute
13	org:resource	String	Event attribute
14	MonthlyCost	Float	Event attribute
15	EventOrigin	String	Event attribute
16	EventID	String	Event attribute
17	Selected	Boolean	Event attribute
18	CreditScore	Integer	Event attribute
19	OfferedAmount	Float	Event attribute

Table 3.1: BPI Challenge 2017 Event Log Overview

contain the same values for all events (rows) of the same case. All other columns would then just be classified as event attributes. However, by taking a closer look at each column it becomes clear that the distinction of event and case attributes is not that trivial. The "Accepted" column for example, has Boolean datatype and will only receive a value after the activity (event, row 2 in table 3.1) *A_Accepted* which usually isn't the first activity of an application (case, row 1) and thus has empty cells for the first activities of most of the cases. The "Accepted" column is likely to be a flag for whether an application got accepted by the financial institute or not and hence should rather be a case attribute. Furthermore, the column "EventOrigin" (row 15) indicates an event's affiliation to one of the different entities of the process, i.e. *Workflow*, *Application* and *Offer*. With the help of this column we can distinguish the event attributes according to their respective entities. Rows 9, 10, 12, 14, 17, 18 and 19 of in table 3.1 contain information about offers. For this process multiple offers can be created for one application which we can distinguish by their "OfferID" (row 12). The "EventOrigin" value *Application* refers to the application and the *Workflow* events enrich the cases with workflow information such that per process instance exactly one application and exactly one workflow exists. Row 13 contains the resource that has been recorded for a certain event. This information is part of many event logs and enables us to apply organizational mining techniques as described in [1].

3.3 Insights

In this section we specify some desired insights that we typically want to derive from an event log. Some are rather generic insights that can be retrieved from any event log as described in section 2.1 and others can be considered more specific to the information contained in BPIC17 log, such as offers, as described in section 3.2.

1. Query a specific attribute of a specific event.
2. Query attributes of cases.
3. Directly follows (DF) relations of events - Event X directly follows event Y in the same case without any events in between them.
4. Eventually follows relationships of events - Event X is eventually followed by event Y in the same case.
5. Case variants - The variant of a case is defined by the sequence of its activities. All cases with the same sequence of activities have the same variant.
6. Handover-of-work (HoW) social network - The resources of two events with directly follows relationship have a handover of work relationship. A social network can be created from the collection of all HoW relationships in the log.
7. Distance between two specific Activities - Distance can be time or activity count between two events with specific activities in one case.
8. Query a sequence of activities which depends on attributes of multiple entities of one case.

For every insight we will define at least one question specific to our case study to be answered in the evaluation section.

4 Representing Event Logs as Graphs

4.1 From Table to Graph

When creating a graph data structure from tabular data, there are multiple ways how the data can be represented. The design of the data structure depends on the purpose the graph is created for. To structure the design decisions for the graph we introduce a simple logic shown in figure 4.1. As discussed in earlier sections, the central elements of an event log are events and cases. Thus we create one node for every case identifier and one node for every event, i.e. row in the log. Additionally there might be other process-related entity identifiers we can derive from the log such as "org:resource" or "OfferID" in our case study as discussed in section 3.2. All other columns might become a property of either of the three node types or just be ignored if deemed irrelevant. However, by only following this generic logic for our node definition we could miss important information. Furthermore we want to take a closer look at the "EventOrigin" column that has also been discussed in section 3.2 already. Next to "Offer", this column indicates the existence of an "Application" and a "Workflow" entity and the latter two don't have discrete identifiers other than the case identifier. At a first glance it might be counter intuitive to establish a distinct "Application" node type next to what we defined as a case in the loan application process. Consider the "Application" as some form that must be filed to start a case, whereas the case as we defined it is actually a combination of "Application", "Offer" and "Workflow" events. This way we can create relationships dedicated for the different aspects of the process more easily.

Figure 4.1: Decision Logic for Node Creation

Table 4.1 shows an overview of the nodes and their properties as discussed above. The *-markings indicate the unique identifier of the respective nodes as property from the event data. The unique identifiers have been implemented as property called "name" to the respective node type. Because the log contains exactly one (*:Application*) and exactly one (*:Workflow*) per case and also due to the lack of a dedicated identifier for these entities, we reused the case identifier. Note that upon creation of a new node or relationship, Neo4j creates an internal unique ID for it. All other properties have been derived from the logic above. Due to the (*:Application*) being the main subject of our definition of a (*:Case*) we decided to turn the case attributes to properties of both node types.

To complete the graph event log we need to create relationships between the new nodes. Table 4.2 gives an overview of the relationships we used in the relationship syntax of Cypher which we introduced in section 2.3 with the labels of end and start node. Except for the relationship properties which, for better readability, are listed in a separate column.

#	Label	Properties as Column Name
1	(:Case)	case* LoanGoal ApplicationType RequestedAmount
2	(:Event)	EventID* EventOrigin startTime completeTime event EventOrigin Action
3	(:Resource)	org:resource*
4	(:Offer)	OfferID* MonthlyCost NumberOfTerms OfferedAmount FirstWithdrawalAmount Selected CreditScore
5	(:Application)	case* LoanGoal ApplicationType RequestedAmount
6	(:Workflow)	case*

Table 4.1: Graph event log nodes

#	Relationship	Properties
1	(:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (:Case)	
2	(:Event) -[:DF]-> (:Event)	Duration between the events
3	(:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (:Event)	
4	(:Offer) -[:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (:Case)	
5	(:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (:Offer)	
6	(:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_APPLICATION]-> (:Application)	
7	(:Application) -[:APPLICATION_TO_CASE]-> (:Case)	
8	(:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_WORKFLOW]-> (:Workflow)	
9	(:Workflow) -[:WORKFLOW_TO_CASE]-> (:Case)	
10	(:Event) -[:O_DF]-> (:Event)	Duration between the events
11	(:Event) -[:A_DF]-> (:Event)	Duration between the events
12	(:Event) -[:W_DF]-> (:Event)	Duration between the events
13	(:Resource) -[:HOW]-> (:Resource)	
14	(:Resource) -[:O_HOW]-> (:Resource)	
15	(:Resource) -[:A_HOW]-> (:Resource)	
16	(:Resource) -[:W_HOW]-> (:Resource)	

Table 4.2: Graph event log relationships

The identification of relationships has been based on the event log characteristics and the insights defined in the previous chapter. The relationship names have been chosen in a way that they should be self-explanatory even without the context of their start and end node type. Table 4.2 shows the list of relationships that we retrieved from the event log. Relationships 1 and 2 are generic enough to be applicable to any graph event log derived from a sequential event log. This is due to the fact that they represent mandatory event log characteristics as relationship 1 associates events with a case and relationship 2 realizes the temporal ordering of events within a case by introducing the directly follows (DF) relationships between the events of a case. Whereas the other relationships depend on the information contained in the individual logs. For example relationship 4 would of course require resource information to be contained in the log.

Where sequential event logs are limited to their case internal order of events and rely on selection and projection to show that data columns belongs to specific instances such as an offer, in a graph-based event log these relationships can be added to the log itself. The `-[:O_DF]->` for example introduces the directly follows relationship for events of offers. Relationship 9 represents a similar relationship, but for events that belong to the "Application" entity only and not to the case, as we discussed in the paragraph for the node creation earlier. With the help of these distinct types of DF relationships we enable views on different types of entities within the log. For example if an event log allows a creation of a "global" hand-over of work (HOW) view, i.e. contains resource information, that shows which resources perform activities before/after one another, we can now narrow this perspective down to the scope of one offer instance just by using the `-[:O_HOW]->` relationship. To improve the readability of our graph and queries, we simplified "Application", "Offer" and "Workflow" to "A", "O" and "W" respectively.

4.2 Data Preparation

The BPI Challenge 2017 comes in .xes format which is not directly supported by Neo4j import functionality, whereas .csv is. Therefore ProM was used to convert the .xes to .csv. The resulting file was then directly loaded by Neo4j or Python for preparation.

Through the course of our research, we realized that the conversion from .xes to .csv format by ProM Light (1.2) had led to some unexpected irregularity in the data as can be seen in appendix A.1. We verified that the combination of "O_Create Offer" directly followed by "O_Created" could reliably determine the attributes to an offer for all inspected cases in a sample set. Under the assumption that this holds for the entire dataset we have been able to make use of this irregularity to assign the offer attribute values to the correct offer identifiers. Furthermore, the converted .csv file appeared to have a quite high number of duplicates. This we cured by "merging" identical rows.

There are two main ways to import data in Neo4j: by using the database API or by import from a .csv file. While the assessment of which of the two ways is better is out of the scope of this research, they have been tested by creating a simple `(:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (:Event timestamp)` structured graph event log. The API has been tested using the `py2neo` package for python and indicated slower import speed. Thus we opted for the Neo4j csv import functionality which allows to import the csv file and query it with Cypher right in the built-in Neo4j Browser.

To enable a fast result validation, we selected a subset of 20 cases of the BPIC17. We chose a subset containing cases of the same variant and cases with one and two offers to account for the concepts of process entities. Please check appendix A for the list of case IDs contained in our sample set.

Furthermore, the determination of `-[:O_DF]->`, `-[:A_DF]->` and `-[:W_DF]->` required some internal ordering index of the respective instance. For example, if one case has two offers, the log will get two

different indices for the offers and one for the case itself. The case index is incremented for all events of a case in the order they appear in the log, whereas the index for the offers will only increase for events with "EventOrigin" = "Offer" and for every offer ID in a case there is a different index. For the workflow and application entities this applies accordingly. A sample case is illustrated in appendix A.3.

As a final preparation step for the Neo4j import, we split the timestamp data into their atomic values year, month, day, hour, minute, second and microsecond. This way we could import the timestamps as "LocalDateTime" datatype in Neo4j which enables us to use temporal functions, e.g. to calculate the duration of activities or the time between two events. Even though a reformatting would also be sufficient for such an import, we decided to go for the "atomic" method since it gives us more control over the different values added to the "LocalDateTime" objects and it appears to be less error prone.

The resulting sample log includes 20 cases, 349 events 22 activities, 50 resources and 25 offers.

4.3 Graph Creation

To create the graph according to the design in section 4.1 we used a sequence of Cypher queries to import the prepared data to Neo4j. The queries can be found in appendix B. Since some of the queries rely on the output of other queries, we recommend to keep the order of the listing in the appendix for replication. These queries have been used for both, creating the graph from the sample and from the full log.

Figure 4.2 shows the schema of the graph event log.

Figure 4.2: Graph DB Schema

The sample graph has been created using a machine with an Intel i7 CPU @ 2.8 GHz with 16 GB of memory. The query that took the longest time to complete was query 3 of appendix B with 0.339 seconds

and the cumulative execution time of all queries is 1.215 seconds. No adjustments of the queries or the DB settings were needed to complete sample graph creation. The implementation with our sample set contains 484 nodes with 6 different node types and 2065 relationships with 16 different relationship types.

Creating the graph from the full log was also successful, but needed some adjustments on the database settings and the queries. In a first step we created unique constraints for the name properties (IDs) of :Event, :Case and :Resource nodes. This does not only ensure uniqueness of these nodes, but also creates indices leading to a better performance of our queries. Using the same machine we used for the sample, the longest query execution took 38.875 seconds and the total execution time of all queries summed up to 156.679 seconds. In this case query 2 had the longest execution time. The initial queries we defined for the graph creation (not included in the report) was less efficient and took a cumulative execution time of roughly 75 minutes. We have been able to significantly improve the query performance by reducing the load csv operations, particularly for query 6 to create the -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]->, by adding the "OfferID" as property to event nodes. The downside of this workaround is that we temporarily write redundant information to the graph, i.e. the "OfferID" and the offer index as properties of (:Event) and (:Offer) nodes such that we can read the required data from the graph instead of the csv file. The temporary data is cleaned up by query 20 taking 1.394 seconds. It was necessary to add "USING PERIODIC COMMIT 1000" as first line to queries 1,2,3 and 5 as shown in appendix B.2 to reduce the memory size needed for the execution. Furthermore the default value of 1 GB for memory usage of the Neo4j DB ("dbms.memory.heap.max_size" parameter) prevented some queries to complete. Increasing the option to 12 GB enabled all queries to finish successfully without running into memory problems for the full log. Less than 12 GB might also be sufficient, but we did not conduct further testing.

The full graph event log has 699338 nodes with 6 different node types and 2811907 relationships with 16 different relationship types.

Note that we solely used Cypher queries to create the relationships in table 4.2. No additional algorithms have been needed, which is usually the case for example to create handover-of-work social networks based on sequential event logs.

5 Querying Graph-based event logs using Cypher

In section 3.3 we identified a set of desired insights we want to get from the log. From each of these insights, a specific question on the data will be derived and get answered by querying the graph structure introduced in chapter 4. In order to evaluate the results, the same question will be answered by analysing the sequential event log with Python or common process mining tools such as ProM or Disco. Note that the validation of correctness of the queries was done with the same sample cases (see appendix A) of the BPIC17 log except for question 19, where the full log was used to check the results for correctness. Additionally, questions that aimed at querying all occurrences of a pattern or property such as for question 5, 8 and 11 have also been evaluated on the full log. All queries have also been executed on the full graph to ensure they actually can be executed and to give an indication on how they perform on the full data. Every query is checked for correctness on the sample graph or full graph and for performance/feasibility always on the full graph.

The case study on the BPIC17 log has been conducted using Neo4j version 3.5.4 using an Intel i7 CPU @ 2.8 GHz with 16 GB of memory.

Depending on the query, Neo4j offers different representations of results, e.g. graph structure similar to figure 2.1 or table format. Therefore, the screenshots might differ per query result. Part (a) of the screenshots always represents the Neo4j output and part (b) the output of the respective tool used on the sequential log.

5.1 Query Attributes of Events

Question 1: What is the completion time of the "A_Submitted" activity of the case "Application_681547497"?

```
1 MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e:Event)
2 WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" AND e.activity = "A_Submitted"
3 RETURN e.completetime
```

The output of the query is shown in figure 5.1a (a). Since we only returned a property, the Neo4j output cannot be visualized as a graph. Figure 5.1b shows the corresponding activity in Disco.

Figure 5.1: Question 1 Screenshots

Note the query returns as many lines as "A_Submitted" activities exist in the case.

We also want to demonstrate that the attributes originally defined as event attributes in table 3.1 have partly been translated to nodes as defined in table 4.1 and some of the other event attributes became attributes of the entity itself, e.g. an offer as entity and the offered amount as node property in the graph: (:Offer {OfferedAmount}). The following query shows that the offered amount can still be queried, but in a different way compared to a property of an :Event node as shown in the query above.

The execution time on the full graph was 0.002 seconds.

Question 2: What are the offered amounts in case "Application_681547497"?

```

1 MATCH (c:Case) <-[:OFFER_TO_CASE]- (o:Offer)
2 WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497"
3 RETURN o.name, o.offeredamount

```

\$ MATCH (c:Case) <-[:OFFER_TO_CASE]- (o:Offer) WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" RETURN o.name, o.offeredamount

o.name	o.offeredamount
"Offer_716078829"	"25000.0"
"Offer_897102764"	"25000.0"

(a)

Activity	Resource	Date	Time	Durati	(case	(case	(case	Accep	Action	Crediti	Event	Event	FirstV	Month	Numt	OfferID	OfferedAmount
1 A_Create Application	User_1	19...	11:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		Cre...		App...	App...					
2 A_Submitted	User_1	19...	11:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
3 A_Concept	User_1	19...	11:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
4 W_Complete application	User_78	21...	14:...	18 ...	Ne...	Car	250...		Del...		Wor...	Wor...					
5 A_Accepted	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
6 O_Create Offer	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	true	Cre...	0	Offe...	Offer	250...	461...	60	Offer_716078829	25000.0
7 O_Created	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_897102764	25000.0
8 O_Create Offer	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	true	Cre...	0	Offe...	Offer	0.0	450.0	63	Offer_716078829	
9 O_Created	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_897102764	
10 O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_897102764	
11 O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_716078829	
12 W_Call after offers	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		Obt...		Wor...	Wor...					
13 A_Complete	User_78	21...	15:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
14 A_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
15 O_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_897102764	
16 O_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08:...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_716078829	

(b)

Figure 5.2: Question 2 Screenshots

Since we have two offers in this case, we get two rows back from the query in Neo4j as can be seen at figure 5.2a. Offers "Offer_716078829" and "Offer_897102764" have both been created for case "Application_681547497" and both with an offered amount of 25000. As we can see on the Disco screenshot in figure 5.2b, we need to make the assumption that "O_Create Offer" directly followed by "O_Created" in the sequential data belong to the same offer to relate an OfferID to its attributes.

The execution time on the full graph was 0.003 seconds.

5.2 Query Attributes of Cases

Querying case attributes works similar to querying event attributes.

Question 3: What was the requested amount in case "Application_681547497"?

```

1 MATCH (c:Case)
2 WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497"
3 RETURN c.requestedamount

```


Figure 5.3: Question 3 Neo4j Screenshot

Besides the fact that we queried a different type of node and property name, there is no difference to querying an event and thus the execution time on the full graph was with 0.003 seconds equally low.

Question 1-3 are concerned about retrieving attributes of single event log elements like case or event.

With **question 4** we combine event and case attributes: **What is the completion time of the "A_Submitted" activity and the loan goal of the case "Application_681547497"?**

With the following Cypher query we can also retrieve both, event and case attributes, at once. It (execution time: 0.083 seconds) has the same output as the question 1 query but additionally returns the "loangoal" property of the case "Application_681547497".

```
1 MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e:Event)
2 WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" AND e.activity = "A_Submitted"
3 RETURN e.completetime, c.loangoal
```

Question 5: What is the completion time of the "A_Submitted" activity and the loan goal all cases?

In case we want to retrieve the same information for all cases, we can remove the restriction for the case "Application_681547497" to include all 20,423 cases with an "A_Submitted" activity in the dataset. As shown in the following query (execution time: 0.944 seconds):

```
1 MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e:Event)
2 WHERE e.activity = "A_Submitted"
3 RETURN e.completetime, c.loangoal
```

The corresponding screenshots can be found at appendix C.1.

5.3 Directly follows relations of events

Here we are going to query the graph for one of the fundamental characteristics of a sequential event log: the directly follows relationships between events. In order to do so, we select the "A_Submitted" activity of case "Application_681547497" we have seen in question 1 already and check for its directly following activity.

Question 6: What activity follows "A_Submitted" in case "Application_681547497"?

```
1 MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e1:Event) <-[:DF]- (e2:Event)
2 WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" AND e1.activity = "A_Submitted"
3 RETURN e1, e2
```


Figure 5.4: Question 6 Neo4j Screenshot

For question 6 we can choose the graph visualization, because the return statement consists of graph elements and not only of properties. Figure 5.4 shows that "A_Concept" directly follows "A_Submitted". The standard visualization of Neo4j Browser shows all relationships between the nodes returned by the query. This is why the *A_DF* relationship is also shown in the screenshot. The execution time on the full graph was 0.009 seconds.

The following question aims at querying the DF relation of events of a particular entity.

Question 7: What activity follows "O_Created" in offer "Offer_716078829"?

```
1 MATCH (o: Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e1: Event) <-[:O_DF]- (e2: Event)
2 WHERE o.name = "Offer_716078829" AND e1.activity = "O_Created"
3 RETURN e1, e2
```

The execution time was 0.174 seconds. To retrieve this information by traditional process mining techniques, the offer identifier is defined as case identifier, meaning that the entire log must be reloaded to realize the new case definition and also required to filter out all non offer events. This has been done for the query verification and the respective screenshots can be inspected in appendix C.1.

Question 8: What activity follows "O_Created" in all offers of the dataset"?

The following query took 11.291 seconds to complete.

```
1 MATCH (o: Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e1: Event) <-[:O_DF]- (e2: Event)
2 WHERE e1.activity = "O_Created"
3 RETURN e1, e2
```

It returned 42,995 node pairs, which means that every offer in the dataset has an "O_Created" followed by some other activity. This could be verified in Disco by applying the same method as for question 7 and additionally filter offers that do not have an "O_Created" activity followed by an activity related to the same offer.

5.4 Eventually follows relationships of events

We now want to see if there is a directly follows relationship between two events with specific activities in case "Application_681547497".

Question 9: Does "A_Accepted" eventually follow "A_Submitted" in case "Application_681547497"?

For this question we don't know how many relationships and nodes need to be walked along the path between "A_Accepted" and "A_Submitted". The only thing we certainly know is that if there is an eventually follows relationship between the two activities, the path will consist of an unknown number of event nodes and DF relationships. For this type of queries we can use the *-operator for the DF relationship. The *-operator considers an arbitrary number of DF relationships to be matched between the event nodes in the MATCH clause.

```
1 MATCH (c: Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e1: Event) <-[:DF*]- (e2: Event)
2 WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" AND e1.activity = "A_Submitted" AND e2.
   activity = "A_Accepted"
3 RETURN e1, e2
```


Figure 5.5: Question 9 Neo4j Screenshot

When only checking for the existence of the eventually follows relationship in question, we get nodes that are not necessarily directly connected, as can be seen in figure 5.5. In this case we only know that they are connected, but the query result does not show how. If we didn't have a matching pattern the result would be empty. The query took 0.022 seconds on the full graph.

To see the respective path(s) between the nodes we are interested in, we can alternatively issue:

```
1 MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e1:Event) <-[:DF*]- (e2:Event)
2 WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" AND e1.activity = "A_Submitted" AND e2.
   activity = "A_Accepted"
3 RETURN (e1:Event) <-[:DF*]- (e2:Event)
```

Which took 0.011 seconds on the full graph.

Figure 5.6: Question 9 Neo4j Screenshot with Path

We also want to know if we can do this for entities.

Question 10: Does "O_Cancelled" eventually follow "O_Created" in offer "Offer_716078829"?

```
1 MATCH (o:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF*]- (e2:Event)
2 WHERE o.name = "Offer_716078829" AND e1.activity = "O_Created" AND e2.activity = "
   O_Cancelled"
3 RETURN e1, e2
```

The query completed in 0.182 seconds and returned two nodes with the respective activities, meaning that the EF relationship in question indeed exists for offer "Offer_716078829". The verification was done with Disco by applying the same load and filter methods as for question 7.

Question 11: Which offer entities contain a "O_Cancelled" eventually follows "O_Created" relationship?

```
1 MATCH (o:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF*]- (e2:Event)
2 WHERE e1.activity = "O_Created" AND e2.activity = "O_Cancelled"
3 RETURN e1, e2
```

The execution time of the query was 11.291 seconds and returned 20,898 records that actually contain an "O_Cancelled" eventually follows "O_Created" relationship. The result can be replicated in Disco by using the offer as case identifier and filter for this EF relationship.

5.5 Case variants

Now let's consider the case variants.

For some analysis it is useful to know what case variant a case, e.g. "Application_681547497", has. With our data model we can simply query for the "variant" property of the case to retrieve the respective case variant id. The respective query completed in 0.006 seconds on the full graph.

```
1 MATCH (c:Case)
2 WHERE c.name = 'Application_681547497'
3 RETURN c.variant
```

The answer is variant number 8 for the sample graph. However, the variant indices will differ from tool to tool and thus are hard to compare. Therefore let us check for the variant with the most traces in the sample.

Question 12: How many traces has the most frequent variant?

```
1 MATCH (c:Case)
2 WITH c.variant as variant, count(*) AS count
3 ORDER BY count DESC
4 LIMIT 1
5 MATCH (c:Case)
6 WHERE c.variant = variant
7 RETURN c.name, variant, count
```

\$ MATCH (c:Case) WITH c.variant as variant, count(*) AS count ORDER BY count DESC LIMIT 1 MATCH (c:Case) WHERE c.variant = variant RETURN c.name, variant, count

c.name	variant	count
"Application_889180637"	"Variant_7"	3
"Application_1065734594"	"Variant_7"	3
"Application_1076724533"	"Variant_7"	3

Figure 5.7: Question 12 Neo4j Screenshot

This shows that the most frequent variant occurs three times in the sample. The screenshot in figure 5.7 and the Disco screenshot in figure C.12 in appendix C show the same case three case ids for the most frequent trace variant. The query completed after 0.237 seconds on the full graph.

The path of the variant on the graph, i.e. a cases' events and their DF relations, might also be of interest.

Question 13: What is the path of events of case "Application_681547497"?

```
1 MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e:Event) <-[:DF*]- (e2:Event)
2 WHERE NOT (e)<-[:DF]-() AND NOT (e2)<-[:DF]-() AND c.name = 'Application_681547497'
3 RETURN (e:Event) <-[:DF*]- (e2:Event) AS paths
```

The query took only 0.023 seconds to complete on the full dataset. It returned the desired path and the verification has been done with Disco as can be seen in the question 13 screenshots in appendix C.1.

5.6 Handover of Work

Now we want to get a handover-of-work social network of our resources.

Question 14: How does the handover-of-work social network look like for the sample set?

```
1 MATCH p = (r1) -[:HOW]-> (r2)
2 RETURN p
```

This returns all handovers of work between resource including selfloops. The resulting graph was compared with the result of the "Mine for a Handover-of-Work Social Network" plugin of ProM 6.8. Since the results are too large to be captured on a single screenshots, we compared parts of them to check if the results correspond. The screenshots can be found in figure C.14 in appendix C. The two screenshots show similar results. The ProM graphs only shows the HOW relationships without self loops, i.e. users performing several consecutive activities. The Neo4j graph contains self loops, but by adding a "WHERE r1.name <> r2.name" clause the query can be adjusted accordingly. We considered the self loops useful information, especially if we take frequencies into account as can be seen in the next query. The graph visualisation of Neo4j also shows all other relationships between the nodes in the results. For better readability the actual HOW relationships are drawn slightly bigger than the others. Please note that this is just a feature of the graph view and the result data does not contain other relationships than HOW. The query took 1.227 seconds to complete on the full graph.

We can add frequencies only by taking the DF relations into account, because HOW relations only indicate that there is a handover, but not how often. We can formulate the following query to take the frequency into account:

```
1 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:  
   RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)  
2 RETURN r1 AS from, r2 AS to, count(*) AS frequency  
3 ORDER BY frequency DESC
```

Note that the count(*) adds the amount of handovers to the table representation of the Neo4j output. The most frequent items of the result for the sample set can be inspected in appendix C.15. Interestingly the most frequent HOW relationships are self loops. The execution time on the full graph was 1.871 seconds.

Similarly, we can edit the query in a way that it returns paths instead of 2 distinct nodes.

```
1 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:  
   RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)  
2 RETURN (r1)-[:HOW]-(r2) as p, count(*) AS frequency
```

With 17.517 this query takes considerably longer to process on the full graph compared to the 1.871 seconds of the query above. The graphical output in Neo4j, however, is equal to the one of the last query (appendix C.15). The difference lies in the format of the data that is returned, i.e. a path vs. 2 distinct nodes per match.

5.7 Handover of Work based on Entities

Now we want to assess a more log-specific view on the handover-of-work domain. Now we only want to consider handovers within offers. Since offers are no typical element of an event log, it is a specific insight to BPIC17.

Question 15: How does the order-based handover-of-work social network look like for the sample set?

```
1 MATCH p = (r1) -[:O_HOW]-> (r2)  
2 RETURN p
```

Like in section 5.6, we again compared a sub-graph of the results in Neo4j and ProM. The screenshots of the ProM and Neo4j graphs can be found in figure C.16. The network mined by ProM required loading the sample log with "OfferID" as case identifier and subsequent filtering of non offer related events prior to the application of the "Mine for a Handover-of-Work Social Network" plugin. Again, except for the self loops, the O_HOW relationships of both graphs are equal. The query took 0.83 seconds to complete on the full graph. Again we can extend the query to take handover frequencies into account:

```

1 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
   RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
2 RETURN r1 AS from, r2 AS to, count(*) AS frequency
3 ORDER BY frequency DESC

```

A partial output for the sample graph can be found in appendix C.17. Similar to the HOW social network, the self loops represent the most frequent O_HOW relationships. The execution time on the full graph was 1.162 seconds.

5.8 Distance between two specific Activities

Here we want to see how long the shortest distance between the creation of an offer and its acceptance is. For the first question to this insight, we consider the distance to be the time between the completion of "O_Created" and the start of "O_Accepted" of an offer.

Question 16: What is the duration of the longest accepted offer in terms of time?

```

1 MATCH (start:Event { activity: "O_Created" }) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o:Offer) <-[:
   EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (end:Event { activity: "O_Accepted" })
2 WITH start, end, duration.between(start.completetime, end.starttime) AS time, o
3 ORDER BY time DESC
4 LIMIT 1
5 RETURN start, end, time.days AS days, (toFloat(time.minutes)/60) AS hours, o

```

The query could be less complex, but the "duration.between()" function returns a rather unusual format, "P0M24DT53003.990000000S" in this case. For better readability the output has been reshaped. Figure C.18 shows the results of the query and a corresponding view in Disco. When rounding up the Neo4j result we get the exact same duration shown in the Disco view for the same offer.

The query took 0.643 seconds to complete on the full graph.

Question 17: What is the duration of the longest accepted offer in terms of activities?

```

1 MATCH (start:Event { activity: "O_Created" }) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (:Offer) <-[:
   EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (end:Event { activity: "O_Accepted" })
2 MATCH p = (start) -[:DF*] - (end)
3 RETURN length(p), (:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (end)
4 ORDER BY length(p) DESC
5 LIMIT 1

```

The length function with a path variable as input returns the "hops" between nodes in the path. The query returns 20, thus the longest sequence of activities from "O_Created" to "O_Accepted" in the sample set consists of 21 activities including the two. By counting the sequence of activities in the Disco screenshot in figure C.19 we also get 21 activities including the two. The query took 2.744 seconds to complete on the full graph.

We can also reduce this question to consider the activities belonging to the offers, similar to question 15 but in the context of duration.

Question 18: What is the duration of the longest accepted offer in terms of offer-specific activities?

```

1 MATCH (start:Event { activity: "O_Created" }) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o:Offer) <-[:
   EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (end:Event { activity: "O_Accepted" })
2 MATCH p = (start) -[:O_DF*] - (end)
3 RETURN length(p), (:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (end)
4 ORDER BY length(p) DESC
5 LIMIT 1

```

The result for this query is 3, thus 4 activities. Taking a closer look revealed that every accepted offer in our sample set took exactly 4 order-related activities from and with "O_Created" to "O_Accepted". The Neo4j result can again be verified by counting the order related activities in figure C.20(b).

The execution time on the full graph was 0.93 seconds. The query on the full graph revealed that every accepted offer in the data set consists of maximum 4 activities.

5.9 Involve multiple Entities

With the last question we want analyse the data for very log specific information. We want to retrieve sequences of activities (paths) per entity of a case, but only for those cases that meet our requirements.

Question 19: What are the paths between "A_Create Application" and "O_Cancelled" for those cases with at least two different offers with "O_Created" directly followed by "O_Cancelled" on the entity level?

This is a typical question that can be considered challenging for today's standard process mining tools using sequential event logs. It requires several steps where the log needs to be analysed and filtered for the different components of the question. Here we need to identify all offers "O_Created" directly followed by "O_Cancelled" on the entity (offer) level. We also need to identify all cases we are interested in, i.e. having at least two of these offers. Only then we can start answering the question and retrieve the sequences of activities between "A_Create Application" and "O_Cancelled" for the individual offers.

Due to the low number of cases that have the desired characteristics, we evaluated this question also for correctness on the full graph.

The following query returns the paths we are looking for:

```
1 MATCH (e1:Event { activity : "O_Created" })<-[:O_DF]-(e2:Event { activity : "
    O_Cancelled" }) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o: Offer) -[:rel:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c: Case)
2 WITH c AS c, count(o) AS ct
3 WHERE ct > 1
4 MATCH (:Event { activity : "O_Created" })<-[:O_DF]-(e:Event { activity : "O_Cancelled" })
    -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o: Offer) -[:rel:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c)
5 WITH e AS O_Cancelled
6 MATCH p = (A_Created:Event { activity : "A_Create Application" }) <-[:DF*]-
    (O_Cancelled:Event { activity : "O_Cancelled" })
7 RETURN p
```

This query took 0.406 seconds to complete on the full graph when using Neo4j Browser. It is a combination of three different queries where the subsequent MATCH clauses can use the output of the preceding selection clauses. The MATCH clause in line 4 can match all cases we are interested in by using the variable "c" and hands the "O_Cancelled" events of the desired offers over to the final query. The final query then returns the paths (DF) from "A_Create Application" to "O_Cancelled" by using the *-operator which gives us the desired result. We get 218 sequences returned, which means we have 218 offers in our output. If we want to include the cases in our output, we can add the "c" variable to the WITH clause in line 5 and include the case in the last part of our query as follows:

```
1 MATCH (e1:Event { activity : "O_Created" })<-[:O_DF]-(e2:Event { activity : "
    O_Cancelled" }) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o: Offer) -[:rel:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c: Case)
2 WITH c AS c, count(o) AS ct
3 WHERE ct > 1
4 MATCH (:Event { activity : "O_Created" })<-[:O_DF]-(e:Event { activity : "O_Cancelled" })
    -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o: Offer) -[:rel:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c)
5 WITH e AS O_Cancelled
6 MATCH p = (A_Created:Event { activity : "A_Create Application" }) <-[:DF*]-
    (O_Cancelled:Event { activity : "O_Cancelled" })
7 RETURN p
```

This query took 0.453 seconds in Neo4j Browser to complete on the full graph.

Due to the complexity of this query the evaluation of the sequential log has been conducted in Python. The script can be found in appendix C.2.1. The results of both, the CSV analysis and the graph analysis

have been included in the script to enable a fast and sound comparison of both outputs. The graph analysis used the latter query to include the cases and both results have been transformed to the same data shape (case id, offer id and the sequence of activities) for better comparability. As we can see in the output of the script (appendix C.2.2) the full data set contains 103 cases with 218 offers with the characteristics in question and both outputs are equal.

Remarkably, the CSV analysis took more than 15 minutes whereas the graph analyses took less than a second on an Intel i7 CPU @ 2.8 GHz with 16 GB of memory with Python. However, a performance comparison is out of scope of this research and both the CSV and graph analysis have not been optimized for efficiency.

6 Conclusion

In this report we have been able to explore a way to represent and query event log data in a graph and we have been able to show that a graph DB and more specific Neo4j is an appropriate way to represent an event log for process mining. To conclude the report we want to verify if we have been able to answer the given research questions:

1. How can the concepts of event logs be represented in graph databases?

We have shown one possible way to represent an event log as property graph. The concepts case, event and activity are represented as property graph elements as well as resources and timestamps. We introduced entities as distinct nodes to make querying the graph on the different process aspects easier. Also the introduction of entity specific directly follows relations, such as O_DF, enabled us to define simple queries to analyse questions that require different filters and projections or special algorithms with sequential event data. In terms of the graph design, many times the question was not "can we represent the data in in a graph for our purpose?" but rather "what is the best way to represent the data in a graph for our purpose?". Because property graphs offer different ways to represent data and our main goal is process mining we combined the standard concepts of sequential event logs and augmented them with additional perspectives such as entities by only using the data available in the sequential log.

a) How can cases and the temporal and causal ordering of events be represented in graphs?

By introducing different types of relationships between the nodes we have been able to model causal and temporal relationships of events, e.g. with `-[:DF]->` relationship. We even could enhance the view by making orders a distinct "entity" that is related to a case, compared to the rather fuzzy representation in a sequential event log where it is not clear whether this is an event attribute or a case attribute.

b) How can attributes and values be stored and shared across cases?

We successfully showed that attributes and their values can be stored as both, nodes or properties to nodes and both ways enable the graph to be queried these attributes over multiple cases.

2. How to use graph-based queries to answer process analysis questions within and across cases?

Chapter 5 was dedicated to demonstrate answering process analysis questions. Starting from simple tasks like querying an attribute value of a specific event or case, we went on to more elaborate questions across cases. We have also been able to query a handover-of-work social network with a single query.

The only shortcoming we could identify, if it can be considered a shortcoming, is the longer total processing times when importing a full log into Neo4j and creating and configuring the database compared to loading the full sequential log into ProM for example. On the other hand, the import usually only takes place once and does not require reloading in order to create new data perspectives. In terms of data representation or retrieval, we have not been facing any issues. We could retrieve the same results compared to the traditional process mining tooling for all the queries in this report. Most remarkably we have been able to perform the complete graph creation and graph analysis on DB level, i.e. by only using Cypher queries. Even though it does not seem likely that all possible process mining questions on graph event data can be answered by solely using Cypher, having a graph database as source for process mining applications can enable deeper insights on processes. For pure data analysis related queries it seems likely to be possible to answer all process mining related queries on BPIC17 based graph design

of this report. For some questions it will even be harder to evaluate the queries by means of conventional process mining tools as we experienced for question 12 in chapter 5. For more sophisticated applications like predictive analytics, for example to predict the remaining cycle time of a case, where mathematical models need to be trained Cypher and Neo4j will not of course suffice, but still can serve as data source.

This report is the first step into a new area in process mining, thus there are manifold research directions that may follow on. For example, a systematic approach for translating sequential event logs to graphs or the creation of a graph event logs for process mining might be required to form the base of new process mining techniques. Graph event logs could for example be extended with more context to the resource perspective, e.g. schedules, to take them into account when assessing process performance. Graph event logs might also be able to contain events of multiple processes that possibly interact, say different processes of the same information system, to again widen the perspective on the processes compared to the isolated process that is usually captured by a sequential event log.

A Data Preparation

A.1 Data Conversion Problem

The following two screenshots show how some of the data got confused by the conversion.

Activity	Resource	Date	Time	Durat	(case	(case	(case	Accep	Action	Credit	EventID	EventOrigin	FirstWithdr	MonthlyCost	Number	OfferID	OfferedAmo	Selected	lifecycle.transition
1 A_Create Application	User_1	19...	11...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	Cre...			Application_681547497	Application							complete
2 A_Submitted	User_1	19...	11...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			AppIState_1893543813	Application							complete
3 A_Concept	User_1	19...	11...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			AppIState_1088174064	Application							complete
4 W_Complete application	User_78	21...	14... 18...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	Del...			Workitem_1321488288	Workflow							complete
5 A_Accepted	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			AppIState_423652521	Application							complete
6 O_Create Offer	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	true Cre...	0		Offer_716078829	Offer	25000.0	461.78	60	Offer_716078829	25000.0	false	complete
7 O_Created	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			OfferState_83386929	Offer							complete
8 O_Create Offer	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	true Cre...	0		Offer_897102764	Offer	0.0	450.0	63	Offer_716078829	25000.0	false	complete
9 O_Created	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			OfferState_1249769519	Offer				Offer_897102764			complete
10 O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			OfferState_1974635109	Offer				Offer_897102764			complete
11 O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			OfferState_1962303803	Offer				Offer_716078829			complete
12 W_Call after offers	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	Obt...			Workitem_19482330	Workflow							start
13 A_Complete	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			AppIState_176442500	Application							complete
14 A_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			AppIState_2057448238	Application							complete
15 O_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			OfferState_1827933237	Offer				Offer_897102764			complete
16 O_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	stat...			OfferState_2142745764	Offer				Offer_716078829			complete

Figure A.1: Offer Information in the .xes File

Activity	Resource	FirstWithdr	Numbe	Accep	OfferID	MonthlyCost	EventID	Selected	Credit	OfferedAmount
1 A_Create Application	User_1						Application_681547497			
2 A_Submitted	User_1						AppIState_1893543813			
3 A_Concept	User_1						AppIState_1088174064			
4 W_Complete application	User_78						Workitem_1321488288			
5 A_Accepted	User_78						AppIState_423652521			
6 O_Create Offer	User_78	25000.0	60	true	Offer_716078829	461.78	Offer_716078829	false	0	25000.0
7 O_Created	User_78	25000.0	60	true	Offer_716078829	461.78	OfferState_83386929	false	0	25000.0
8 O_Create Offer	User_78	0.0	63	true	Offer_897102764	450.0	Offer_897102764	false	0	25000.0
9 O_Created	User_78	0.0	63	true	Offer_897102764	450.0	OfferState_1249769519	false	0	25000.0
10 O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	0.0	63	true	Offer_897102764	450.0	OfferState_1974635109	false	0	25000.0
11 O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	0.0	63	true	Offer_716078829	450.0	OfferState_1962303803	false	0	25000.0
12 W_Call after offers	User_78	0.0	63	true	Offer_716078829	450.0	Workitem_19482330	false	0	25000.0
13 A_Complete	User_78	0.0	63	true	Offer_716078829	450.0	AppIState_176442500	false	0	25000.0
14 A_Cancelled	User_1	0.0	63	true	Offer_716078829	450.0	AppIState_2057448238	false	0	25000.0
15 O_Cancelled	User_1	0.0	63	true	Offer_897102764	450.0	OfferState_1827933237	false	0	25000.0
16 O_Cancelled	User_1	0.0	63	true	Offer_716078829	450.0	OfferState_2142745764	false	0	25000.0

Figure A.2: Offer Information in the .csv File

A.2 Sample Set

#	Case ID
1	Application_2045572635
2	Application_2014483796
3	Application_1973871032
4	Application_1389621581
5	Application_1564472847
6	Application_430577010
7	Application_889180637
8	Application_1065734594
9	Application_681547497
10	Application_1020381296
11	Application_180427873
12	Application_2103964126
13	Application_55972649
14	Application_1076724533
15	Application_1639247005
16	Application_1465025013
17	Application_1244956957
18	Application_1974117177
19	Application_797323371
20	Application_1631297810

Table A.1: Sample Case IDs

A.3 Instance Indices

..	case	event	OfferID	case_index	offer_index	application_index	workflow_index	variant_index
	Application_2045572635	O_Accepted	Offer_2024854898	295089	5	0	0	Variant_1
	Application_2045572635	A_Pending	Offer_2024854898	295090	0	6	0	Variant_1
	Application_2014483796	A_Create Application		20405	0	1	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	A_Submitted		20406	0	2	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	A_Concept		20407	0	3	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	W_Complete application		20408	0	0	1	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	A_Accepted		20409	0	4	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Create Offer	Offer_535822658	20410	1	0	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Created	Offer_535822658	20411	2	0	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Sent (mail and online)	Offer_535822658	20412	3	0	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	W_Call after offers	Offer_535822658	20413	0	0	2	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	A_Complete	Offer_535822658	20414	0	5	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Create Offer	Offer_1647347263	20415	1	0	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Created	Offer_1647347263	20416	2	0	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Sent (mail and online)	Offer_1647347263	20417	3	0	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	A_Cancelled	Offer_1647347263	20418	0	6	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Cancelled	Offer_1647347263	20419	4	0	0	Variant_2
	Application_2014483796	O_Cancelled	Offer_535822658	20420	4	0	0	Variant_2

Figure A.3: Indices for the different Instances

A.4 Python Script for Data Preparation

The Python script used for the data preparation of the sample. The same script has been used for the preparation of the full dataset by using "sampleIds = cases".

```

1 import pandas as pd
2
3 loan_raw = pd.read_csv('bpiChallenge17.csv', keep_default_na=False) #load full log
   from csv
4 loan_raw.drop_duplicates(keep='first', inplace=True) #remove duplicates from the
   dataset
5 loan_raw = loan_raw.reset_index(drop=True) #renew the index to close gaps of
   removed duplicates
6
7 cases = loan_raw.case.unique().tolist() # create a list of all cases in the dataset
8
9 #hard coded case IDs to ease replication
10 sampleIds = ['Application_2045572635',
11              'Application_2014483796',
12              'Application_1973871032',
13              'Application_1389621581',
14              'Application_1564472847',
15              'Application_430577010',
16              'Application_889180637',
17              'Application_1065734594',
18              'Application_681547497',
19              'Application_1020381296',
20              'Application_180427873',
21              'Application_2103964126',

```

```

22     'Application_55972649',
23     'Application_1076724533',
24     'Application_1639247005',
25     'Application_1465025013',
26     'Application_1244956957',
27     'Application_1974117177',
28     'Application_797323371',
29     'Application_1631297810']
30
31 sampleList = [] #create a list (of lists) for the sample data containing a list of
    events for each of the selected cases
32 variants = [] # helper list for the variants
33 for case in sampleIds:
34     offers = [] #helper list for counting the events with eventOrigin = Offer
35     applications = 0 #helper variable for counting the events with eventOrigin =
    Application
36     workflows = 0 #helper variable for counting the events with eventOrigin =
    workflows
37     variant = [] # helper list for the variant of the current case
38     for index, row in loan_raw[loan_raw.case == case].iterrows(): #first iteration
    through the cases for variant detection
39         variant.append(row['event'])
40         if not variant in variants: #if variant of the current case has not been
    observed before, add to the variants list
41             variants.append(variant)
42         for index, row in loan_raw[loan_raw.case == case].iterrows(): #second iteration
    through the cases for adding data
43             if row['event'] == "O_Create Offer": # this activity belongs to an offer
    but has no offer ID
44                 if loan_raw.loc[index+1]['event'] == 'O_Created':#if next activity is "
    O_Created" (always directly follows "O_Create Offer" [verified with Disco])
45                     row['OfferID'] = loan_raw.loc[index+1]['OfferID'] #assign the
    offerID of the next event (O_Created) to this activity
46                     rowList = list(row) #add the event data to rowList
47                     rowList.append(index) #add global index for the sequence of events
48                     if row['EventOrigin'] == 'Offer' and "Offer_" in row['OfferID']: #check if
    event has an offer ID and is an offer event
49                         offers.append(row['OfferID'])#add offerID entry to helper list
50                         rowList.extend([offers.count(row['OfferID']),0,0,"Variant_" + str(
    variants.index(variant)+1)]) #add order index for offer and variant
51                     elif (row['EventOrigin'] == 'Application'):
52                         applications += 1
53                         rowList.extend([0, applications, 0, "Variant_" + str(variants.index(
    variant)+1)])#add order index for application and variant
54                     elif (row['EventOrigin'] == 'Workflow'):
55                         workflows += 1
56                         rowList.extend([0,0, workflows, "Variant_" + str(variants.index(variant)
    +1)])#add order index for workflow and variant
57                     else: # add -1 as default indices for easy detection of undesired outcomes
58                         rowList.extend([-1,-1,-1,"Variant_" + str(variants.index(variant)+1)])
59                     sampleList.append(rowList) #add the extended, single row to the sample
    dataset
60
61 header = list(loan_raw) #save the original header data
62 header.extend(['case_index', 'offer_index', 'application_index', 'workflow_index', '
    variant_index']) #extend the header for the indices created for case, offer,
    application, workflow and variant
63 loan_samples = pd.DataFrame(sampleList, columns=header) #create pandas dataframe and
    add the samples
64
65 # reformat time data for neo4j import
66 loan_samples['startTime'] = pd.to_datetime(loan_samples['startTime'])
67 loan_samples['completeTime'] = pd.to_datetime(loan_samples['completeTime'])

```

```

68
69 #create separate columns (year/month/day/hour/minute/second/microsecond) for
    importing datetime values into neo4j as datetime object
70 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(sY=loan_samples['startTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    year))
71 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(sM=loan_samples['startTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    month))
72 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(sD=loan_samples['startTime'].map(lambda x: x.day
    ))
73 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(sHH=loan_samples['startTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    hour))
74 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(sMM=loan_samples['startTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    minute))
75 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(sSS=loan_samples['startTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    second))
76 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(sMS=loan_samples['startTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    microsecond))
77 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(cY=loan_samples['completeTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    year))
78 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(cM=loan_samples['completeTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    month))
79 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(cD=loan_samples['completeTime'].map(lambda x: x.
    day))
80 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(cHH=loan_samples['completeTime'].map(lambda x: x
    .hour))
81 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(cMM=loan_samples['completeTime'].map(lambda x: x
    .minute))
82 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(cSS=loan_samples['completeTime'].map(lambda x: x
    .second))
83 loan_samples = loan_samples.assign(cMS=loan_samples['completeTime'].map(lambda x: x
    .microsecond))
84
85 if not (any(loan_samples.offer_index == -1) or any(loan_samples.application_index
    == -1) or any(loan_samples.workflow_index == -1)): #check if any event has an
    invalid index
86 #write to file
87 sampleFile = 'loan_sample.csv'
88 loan_samples.to_csv(sampleFile, index=False)
89 print('Data preparation successful – data written to file for Neo4j import')
90 else:
91 print('NO FILE WRITTEN – DATAPREP NOT SUCCESSFUL')

```

B Implementation

The "loan_sample.csv" file must be placed in the import folder of the Neo4j DB you are working with. Comment lines denoted by a leading "//" contain the query number, a short description and the Neo4j output in parenthesis. The graph database has been constructed with the following queries:

B.1 Sample Graph

```
1 //1 create case nodes with case attributes (Added 20 labels , created 20 nodes , set
   100 properties , completed after 274 ms.)
2 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM " file :/// loan_sample.csv" as line
3 WITH line.case as case ,
4   line.LoanGoal as loanGoal ,
5   line.ApplicationType as applicationType ,
6   line.RequestedAmount as requestedAmount ,
7   line.FirstWithdrawalAmount as firstAmount ,
8   line.NumberOfTerms as n_Terms ,
9   line.variant_index as vIndex
10 MERGE (c:Case {name: case , variant: vIndex , loangoal: loanGoal , applicationtype:
   applicationType , requestedamount: toInteger(requestedAmount)})
11
12 //2 create event nodes with event attributes and relationships to cases (Added 349
   labels , created 349 nodes , set 3743 properties , created 349 relationships ,
   completed after 274 ms.)
13 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM " file :/// loan_sample.csv" as line
14 WITH line.case as case ,
15   line.EventID as event ,
16   line.EventOrigin as eventClass ,
17   line.event as activity ,
18   line.Action as action ,
19   line.startTime as startTime ,
20   line.completeTime as completeTime ,
21   line.OfferID as offer ,
22   line.case_index as cIndex ,
23   line.offer_index as oIndex ,
24   line.application_index as aIndex ,
25   line.workflow_index as wIndex ,
26   line.sY as sY , line.sD as sD , line.sM as sM , line.sHH as sHH , line.sMM as sMM ,
   line.sSS as sSS , line.sMS as sMS ,
27   line.cY as cY , line.cD as cD , line.cM as cM , line.cHH as cHH , line.cMM as cMM ,
   line.cSS as cSS , line.cMS as cMS
28 MATCH (c:Case {name: case })
29 CREATE (e:Event {name: event ,
30   starttime: localtime({ year: toInteger(sY) , month: toInteger(sM) , day: toInteger(
   sD) , hour: toInteger(sHH) , minute: toInteger(sMM) , second: toInteger(sSS) ,
   microsecond: toInteger(sMS) }) ,
31   compleatetime: localtime({ year: toInteger(cY) , month: toInteger(cM) , day:
   toInteger(cD) , hour: toInteger(cHH) , minute: toInteger(cMM) , second: toInteger(cSS)
   , microsecond: toInteger(cMS) }) ,
32   activity: activity , class: eventClass , action: action , offerid: offer , caseindex:
   toInteger(cIndex) , offerindex: toInteger(oIndex) , applicationindex: toInteger(
   aIndex) , workflowindex: toInteger(wIndex) })
33 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c)
34
35 //3 create nodes for each resource and edges to event nodes (Added 50 labels ,
   created 50 nodes , set 50 properties , created 349 relationships , completed after
   339 ms.)
36 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM " file :/// loan_sample.csv" as line
37 WITH line.resource as resource , line.EventID as event
38 MATCH (e:Event {name: event })
```

```

39 MERGE (r:Resource {name: resource })
40 CREATE (r) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e)
41
42 //4 create directly follows relationships for events (Table Set 329 properties ,
    created 329 relationships , completed after 82 ms.)
43 MATCH (e1:Event) --> (c:Case) <-- (e2:Event)
44 WHERE e2.caseindex - e1.caseindex = 1
45 CREATE (e2) -[:DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime)
    }]-> (e1)
46
47 //5 create offers , relationships offer -> case (Added 25 labels , created 25 nodes ,
    set 150 properties , created 25 relationships , completed after 32 ms.)
48 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM "file:///loan_sample.csv" as line
49 WITH line.case as case ,
50     line.event as activity ,
51     line.RequestedAmount as requestedAmount ,
52     line.FirstWithdrawalAmount as firstAmount ,
53     line.NumberOfTerms as n_Terms ,
54     line.OfferID as offer ,
55     line.resource as resource ,
56     line.MonthlyCost as monthlyCost ,
57     line.CreditScore as creditScore ,
58     line.OfferedAmount as offeredAmount
59 MATCH(c:Case {name: case }) , (r:Resource {name: resource })
60 WHERE activity = "O_Created"
61 CREATE (o:Offer {name: offer , firstamount: firstAmount , n_terms: n_Terms ,
    monthlycost: monthlyCost , offeredamount: offeredAmount , creditscore: creditScore
    })
62 CREATE (o) -[:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c)
63
64 //6 create relationships offer -> event to associate (Offer)events with offers (
    Created 113 relationships , completed after 19 ms.)
65 MATCH (e:Event) , (o:Offer)
66 WHERE o.name = e.offerid AND e.offerindex > 0
67 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o)
68
69 //7 create application nodes , (Added 20 labels , created 20 nodes , set 80
    properties , completed after 2 ms.)
70 MATCH (c:Case)
71 CREATE (a:Application {name: c.name , loangoal: c.loangoal , applicationtype: c.
    applicationtype , requestedamount: c.requestedamount})
72
73 //8 create relationships application -> case (Created 20 relationships , completed
    after 3 ms.)
74 MATCH (c:Case) , (a:Application)
75 WHERE c.name = a.name
76 CREATE (a) -[:APPLICATION_TO_CASE]-> (c)
77
78 //9 create relationships application -> event to associate (application)events with
    application (Created 156 relationships , completed after 5 ms.)
79 MATCH (e:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:APPLICATION_TO_CASE]- (a:
    Application)
80 WHERE e.class = "Application"
81 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_APPLICATION]-> (a)
82
83 //10 create workflow nodes , (Added 20 labels , created 20 nodes , set 20 properties ,
    completed after 2 ms.)
84 MATCH (c:Case)
85 CREATE (w:Workflow {name: c.name})
86
87 //11 relationships workflow -> case (Created 20 relationships , completed after 2 ms
    .)
88 MATCH (c:Case) , (w:Workflow)

```

```

89 WHERE c.name = w.name
90 CREATE (w) -[:WORKFLOW_TO_CASE]-> (c)
91
92 //12 create relationships workflow -> event to associate (workflow)events with
    workflow (Created 80 relationships , completed after 4 ms.)
93 MATCH (e:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:WORKFLOW_TO_CASE]- (w:Workflow)
94 WHERE e.class = "Workflow"
95 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_WORKFLOW]-> (w)
96
97 //13 create event chain of offers (Set 88 properties , created 88 relationships ,
    completed after 5 ms.)
98 MATCH (e1:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e2:Event)
99 WHERE e2.offerindex - e1.offerindex = 1
100 CREATE (e2) -[:O_DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime)
    }]-> (e1)
101
102 //14 create application based directly follows relationships (Set 136 properties ,
    created 136 relationships , completed after 15 ms.)
103 MATCH (e1:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e2:Event)
104 WHERE e2.applicationindex - e1.applicationindex = 1 AND e1.applicationindex > 0
105 CREATE (e1) <-[:A_DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime)
    }]- (e2)
106
107 //15 create workflow based directly follows relationships (Set 60 properties ,
    created 60 relationships , completed after 7 ms.)
108 MATCH (e1:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e2:Event)
109 WHERE e2.workflowindex - e1.workflowindex = 1 AND e1.workflowindex > 0
110 CREATE (e1) <-[:W_DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime)
    }]- (e2)
111
112 //16 create case-based handover of work relationships (Created 132 relationships ,
    completed after 47 ms.)
113 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
    RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
114 MERGE (r1) -[:HOW]-> (r2)
115
116 //17 create offer-based handover of work relationships (Created 55 relationships ,
    completed after 7 ms.)
117 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
    RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
118 MERGE (r1) -[:O_HOW]-> (r2)
119
120 //18 create application-based handover of work relationships (Created 95
    relationships , completed after 11 ms.)
121 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:A_DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
    RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
122 MERGE (r1) -[:A_HOW]-> (r2)
123
124 //19 create workflow-based handover of work relationships (Created 58 relationships
    , completed after 7 ms.)
125 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:W_DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
    RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
126 MERGE (r1) -[:W_HOW]-> (r2)
127
128 //20 clean up temporary data (Set 602 properties , completed after 78 ms.)
129 MATCH (e:Event)
130 REMOVE e.offerid , e.offerindex

```

B.2 Full Graph

```

1 //create unique constraints for event , case and resource ids (perform one by one)
2 CREATE CONSTRAINT ON (e:Event) ASSERT e.name IS UNIQUE;

```

```

3 CREATE CONSTRAINT ON (c:Case) ASSERT c.name IS UNIQUE;
4 CREATE CONSTRAINT ON (r:Resource) ASSERT r.name IS UNIQUE;
5
6 //1 create case nodes with case attributes (Added 31509 labels , created 31509 nodes
  , set 157545 properties , completed after 15973 ms.)
7 USING PERIODIC COMMIT 1000
8 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM "file:///loan_full.csv" as line
9 WITH line.case as case ,
10  line.LoanGoal as loanGoal ,
11  line.ApplicationType as applicationType ,
12  line.RequestedAmount as requestedAmount ,
13  line.FirstWithdrawalAmount as firstAmount ,
14  line.NumberOfTerms as n_Terms ,
15  line.variant_index as vIndex
16 MERGE (c:Case {name: case , variant: vIndex , loangoal: loanGoal , applicationtype:
  applicationType , requestedamount: toInteger(requestedAmount)})
17
18 //2 create event nodes with event attributes and relationships to cases (Added
  561671 labels , created 561671 nodes , set 6029756 properties , created 561671
  relationships , completed after 38875 ms.)
19 USING PERIODIC COMMIT 1000
20 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM "file:///loan_full.csv" as line
21 WITH line.case as case ,
22  line.EventID as event ,
23  line.EventOrigin as eventClass ,
24  line.event as activity ,
25  line.Action as action ,
26  line.startTime as startTime ,
27  line.completeTime as completeTime ,
28  line.OfferID as offer ,
29  line.case_index as cIndex ,
30  line.offer_index as oIndex ,
31  line.application_index as aIndex ,
32  line.workflow_index as wIndex ,
33  line.sY as sY , line.sD as sD , line.sM as sM , line.sHH as sHH , line.sMM as sMM ,
  line.sSS as sSS , line.sMS as sMS ,
34  line.cY as cY , line.cD as cD , line.cM as cM , line.cHH as cHH , line.cMM as cMM ,
  line.cSS as cSS , line.cMS as cMS
35 MATCH (c:Case {name: case })
36 CREATE (e:Event {name: event ,
37  starttime: localtime({year:toInteger(sY) , month:toInteger(sM) , day:toInteger(
  sD) , hour:toInteger(sHH) , minute:toInteger(sMM) , second:toInteger(sSS) ,
  microsecond:toInteger(sMS) }) ,
38  compleatetime: localtime({year:toInteger(cY) , month:toInteger(cM) , day:
  toInteger(cD) , hour:toInteger(cHH) , minute:toInteger(cMM) , second:toInteger(cSS)
  , microsecond:toInteger(cMS) }) ,
39  activity: activity , class: eventClass , action: action , offerid: offer , caseindex:
  toInteger(cIndex) , offerindex: toInteger(oIndex) , applicationindex: toInteger(
  aIndex) , workflowindex: toInteger(wIndex)})
40 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c)
41
42 //3 create nodes for each resource and edges to event nodes (Added 145 labels ,
  created 145 nodes , set 145 properties , created 561671 relationships , completed
  after 17200 ms.)
43 USING PERIODIC COMMIT 1000
44 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM "file:///loan_full.csv" as line
45 WITH line.resource as resource , line.EventID as event
46 MATCH (e:Event {name: event })
47 MERGE (r:Resource {name: resource })
48 CREATE (r) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e)
49
50 //4 create directly follows relationships for events (Set 530162 properties ,
  created 530162 relationships , completed after 22645 ms.)

```

```

51 MATCH (e1:Event) --> (c:Case) <-- (e2:Event)
52 WHERE e2.caseindex - e1.caseindex = 1
53 CREATE (e2) -[:DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime)
    }]-> (e1)
54
55 //5 create offers , relationships offer -> case (Added 42995 labels , created 42995
    nodes , set 257970 properties , created 42995 relationships , completed after 10830
    ms.)
56 USING PERIODIC COMMIT 1000
57 LOAD CSV WITH HEADERS FROM "file:///loan_full.csv" as line
58 WITH line.case as case ,
59     line.event as activity ,
60     line.RequestedAmount as requestedAmount ,
61     line.FirstWithdrawalAmount as firstAmount ,
62     line.NumberOfTerms as n_Terms ,
63     line.OfferID as offer ,
64     line.resource as resource ,
65     line.MonthlyCost as monthlyCost ,
66     line.CreditScore as creditScore ,
67     line.OfferedAmount as offeredAmount
68 MATCH(c:Case {name: case}), (r:Resource {name: resource})
69 WHERE activity = "O_Created"
70 CREATE (o:Offer {name: offer , firstamount: firstAmount , n_terms: n_Terms ,
    monthlycost: monthlyCost , offeredamount: offeredAmount , creditscore: creditScore
    })
71 CREATE (o) -[:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c)
72
73 //6 create relationships offer -> event to associate (Offer)events with offers (
    Created 193849 relationships , completed after 1299 ms.)
74 MATCH (e:Event) , (o:Offer)
75 WHERE o.name = e.offerid AND e.offerindex > 0
76 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o)
77
78 //7 create application nodes , (Added 31509 labels , created 31509 nodes , set 126036
    properties , completed after 298 ms.)
79 MATCH (c:Case)
80 CREATE (a:Application {name: c.name , loangoal: c.loangoal , applicationtype: c.
    applicationtype , requestedamount: c.requestedamount})
81
82 //8 create relationships application -> case (Created 31509 relationships ,
    completed after 423 ms.)
83 MATCH (c:Case) , (a:Application)
84 WHERE c.name = a.name
85 CREATE (a) -[:APPLICATION_TO_CASE]-> (c)
86
87 //9 create relationships application -> event to associate (application)events with
    application (Created 239595 relationships , completed after 1209 ms.)
88 MATCH (e:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:APPLICATION_TO_CASE]- (a:
    Application)
89 WHERE e.class = "Application"
90 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_APPLICATION]-> (a)
91
92 //10 create workflow nodes , (Added 31509 labels , created 31509 nodes , set 31509
    properties , completed after 152 ms.)
93 MATCH (c:Case)
94 CREATE (w:Workflow {name: c.name})
95
96 //11 relationships workflow -> case(Created 31509 relationships , completed after
    383 ms.)
97 MATCH (c:Case) , (w:Workflow)
98 WHERE c.name = w.name
99 CREATE (w) -[:WORKFLOW_TO_CASE]-> (c)
100

```

```

101 //12 create relationships workflow -> event to associate (workflow)events with
      workflow (Created 128227 relationships , completed after 813 ms.)
102 MATCH (e:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:WORKFLOW_TO_CASE]- (w:Workflow)
103 WHERE e.class = "Workflow"
104 CREATE (e) -[:EVENT_TO_WORKFLOW]-> (w)
105
106 //13 create event chain of offers (Set 150854 properties , created 150854
      relationships , completed after 2248 ms.)
107 MATCH (e1:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e2:Event)
108 WHERE e2.offerindex - e1.offerindex = 1
109 CREATE (e2) -[:O_DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime
      )}]> (e1)
110
111 //14 create application based directly follows relationships (Set 208086 properties
      , created 208086 relationships , completed after 10294 ms.)
112 MATCH (e1:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e2:Event)
113 WHERE e2.applicationindex - e1.applicationindex = 1 AND e1.applicationindex > 0
114 CREATE (e1) <-[:A_DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime
      )}]> (e2)
115
116 //15 create workflow based directly follows relationships (Set 96727 properties ,
      created 96727 relationships , completed after 5218 ms.)
117 MATCH (e1:Event) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e2:Event)
118 WHERE e2.workflowindex - e1.workflowindex = 1 AND e1.workflowindex > 0
119 CREATE (e1) <-[:W_DF {timebetween: duration.between(e1.completetime , e2.starttime
      )}]> (e2)
120
121 //16 create case-based handover of work relationships (Created 11181 relationships ,
      completed after 15588 ms.)
122 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
      RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
123 MERGE (r1) -[:HOW]-> (r2)
124
125 //17 create offer-based handover of work relationships (Created 6313 relationships ,
      completed after 3739 ms.)
126 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
      RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
127 MERGE (r1) -[:O_HOW]-> (r2)
128
129 //18 create application-based handover of work relationships (Created 8205
      relationships , completed after 5716 ms.)
130 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:A_DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
      RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
131 MERGE (r1) -[:A_HOW]-> (r2)
132
133 //19 create workflow-based handover of work relationships (Created 9353
      relationships , completed after 3591 ms.)
134 MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:W_DF]- (e2:Event) <-[:
      RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]- (r2:Resource)
135 MERGE (r1) -[:W_HOW]-> (r2)
136
137 //20 clean up temporary data (Set 974717 properties , completed after 1394 ms.)
138 MATCH (e:Event)
139 REMOVE e.offerid , e.offerindex

```

C Screenshots

This appendix includes all screenshots and python scripts for the queries in chapter 5. Picture (a) is always the Neo4j screenshot and picture (b) is always a screenshot of a tool used with the sequential log. Note that the screenshots do not contain the actual execution times mentioned in the previous chapters. The screenshots have been created after the initial experiment evaluation.

C.1 Questions Screenshots

(a)

(b)

Figure C.1: Question 1 Screenshots

(a)

	Activity	Resource	Date	Time	Durati	(case)	(case)	(case) RequestedAmount	Acce
1	A_Create Application	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:38	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
2	A_Submitted	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:39	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
3	A_Concept	User_1	19.11.2016	11:41:24	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
4	W_Complete application	User_78	21.11.2016	14:56:40	18 ...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
5	A_Accepted	User_78	21.11.2016	15:02:04	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
6	O_Create Offer	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:54	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	true
7	O_Created	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:55	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
8	O_Create Offer	User_78	21.11.2016	15:12:47	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	true
9	O_Created	User_78	21.11.2016	15:12:48	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
10	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
11	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
12	W_Call after offers	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
13	A_Complete	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
14	A_Cancelled	User_1	22.12.2016	08:00:45	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
15	O_Cancelled	User_1	22.12.2016	08:00:45	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	
16	O_Cancelled	User_1	22.12.2016	08:00:45	0 m...	Ne...	Car	25000.0	

(b)

Figure C.3: Question 3 Screenshots

```
$ MATCH (c:Case) <-[:OFFER_TO_CASE]- (o:Offer) WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" RETURN o.name, o.offeredamount
```

o.name	o.offeredamount
"Offer_716078829"	"25000.0"
"Offer_897102764"	"25000.0"

(a)

	Activity	Resource	Date	Time	Durati	(case	(case	(case	Accep	Action	Credit	Event	Event	FirstV	Month	Num:	OfferID	OfferedAmount
1	A_Create Application	User_1	19...	11...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		Cre...		App...	App...					
2	A_Submitted	User_1	19...	11...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
3	A_Concept	User_1	19...	11...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
4	W_Complete application	User_78	21...	14...	18 ...	Ne...	Car	250...		Del...		Wor...	Wor...					
5	A_Accepted	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
6	O_Create Offer	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	true	Cre...	0	Offe...	Offer	250...	461...	60	Offer_716078829	25000.0
7	O_Created	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_897102764	25000.0
8	O_Create Offer	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...	true	Cre...	0	Offe...	Offer	0.0	450.0	63	Offer_897102764	25000.0
9	O_Created	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_897102764	
10	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_716078829	
11	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_716078829	
12	W_Call after offers	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		Obt...		Wor...	Wor...					
13	A_Complete	User_78	21...	15...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
14	A_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		App...	App...					
15	O_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_897102764	
16	O_Cancelled	User_1	22...	08...	0 m...	Ne...	Car	250...		stat...		Offe...	Offer				Offer_716078829	

(b)

Figure C.2: Question 2 Screenshots

```
$ MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e:Event) WHERE c.name = "Application_681547497" AND e.activity = "A_Submitted" RETURN e.completetime, c.loangoal
```

e.completetime	c.loangoal
"2016-11-19T11:40:39.911000000"	"Car"

(a)

Application_681547497

Case with 16 events

Events 16

Start 19.11.2016 11:40:38

Duration 32 days, 20 hours

Active time 0.04 %

Graph Table

	Activity	Resource	Date	Time	Duration	LoanGoal	ApplicationType	RequestedAmount
1	A_Create Application	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:38	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
2	A_Submitted	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:39	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
3	A_Concept	User_1	19.11.2016	11:41:24	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
4	W_Complete application	User_78	21.11.2016	14:56:40	18 mins, 8 secs	Car	New credit	25000.0
5	A_Accepted	User_78	21.11.2016	15:02:04	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
6	O_Create Offer	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:54	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
7	O_Created	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:55	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
8	O_Create Offer	User_78	21.11.2016	15:12:47	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
9	O_Created	User_78	21.11.2016	15:12:48	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
10	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
11	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
12	W_Call after offers	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
13	A_Complete	User_78	21.11.2016	15:14:48	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
14	A_Cancelled	User_1	22.12.2016	08:00:45	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
15	O_Cancelled	User_1	22.12.2016	08:00:45	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0
16	O_Cancelled	User_1	22.12.2016	08:00:45	0 millis	Car	New credit	25000.0

(b)

Figure C.4: Question 4 Screenshots

```
$ MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e:Event) WHERE e.activity = "A_Submitted" RETURN e.completetime, c.loangoal
```

e.completetime	c.loangoal
"2016-01-01T10:51:15.352000000"	"Existing loan takeover"
"2016-01-01T11:16:11.549000000"	"Home improvement"
"2016-01-01T12:19:38.235000000"	"Home improvement"
"2016-01-01T13:34:53.950000000"	"Car"
"2016-01-01T14:00:04.398000000"	"Home improvement"
"2016-01-01T14:05:19.901000000"	"Existing loan takeover"

Started streaming 20423 records in less than 1 ms and completed after 504 ms, displaying first 1000 rows.

(a)

(b)

Figure C.5: Question 5 Screenshots

(a)

	Activity	Resource	Date	Time
1	A_Create Application	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:38
2	A_Submitted	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:39
3	A_Concept	User_1	19.11.2016	11:41:24
4	W_Complete application	User_78	21.11.2016	14:56:40
5	A_Accepted	User_78	21.11.2016	15:02:04
6	O_Create Offer	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:54
7	O_Created	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:55

(b)

Figure C.6: Question 6 Screenshots

(a)

(b)

Figure C.7: Question 7 Screenshots

\$ MATCH (o:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF]- (e2:Event) WHERE e1.activity = "O_Created" RETURN e1, e2

e1

```
{
  "activity": "O_Created",
  "applicationindex": 0,
  "completetime": "2016-02-25T19:17:46.146000000",
  "caseindex": 74697,
  "workflowindex": 0,
  "name": "OfferState_1794495854",
  "action": "statechange",
  "starttime": "2016-02-25T19:17:46.146000000",
  "class": "Offer"
}
```

e2

```
{
  "activity": "O_Sent (mail and online)",
  "applicationindex": 0,
  "caseindex": 74698,
  "workflowindex": 0,
  "completetime": "2016-02-25T19:18:00.090000000",
  "name": "OfferState_675745322",
  "action": "statechange",
  "starttime": "2016-02-25T19:18:00.090000000",
  "class": "Offer"
}
```

Started streaming 42995 records after 1 ms and completed after 11397 ms, displaying first 1000 rows.

(a)

Events	193,849
Cases	42,995
Activities	8
Median case duration	15.9 d
Mean case duration	19.1 d
Start	02.01.2016 10:17:05
End	01.02.2017 12:23:42

(b)

Figure C.8: Question 8 Screenshots

(a)

(b)

	Activity	Resource	Date	Time
1	A_Create Application	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:38
2	A_Submitted	User_1	19.11.2016	11:40:39
3	A_Concept	User_1	19.11.2016	11:41:24
4	W_Complete application	User_78	21.11.2016	14:56:40
5	A_Accepted	User_78	21.11.2016	15:02:04
6	O_Create Offer	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:54
7	O_Created	User_78	21.11.2016	15:11:55

(c)

Figure C.9: Question 9 Screenshots

(a)

(b)

Figure C.10: Question 10 Screenshots

\$ MATCH (o:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF*]- (e2:Event) WHERE e1.activity = "O_Created" AND e2.activity = "O_Cancelled" RETURN e1, e2

e1

```
{
  "activity": "O_Created",
  "applicationindex": 0,
  "completetime": "2016-02-24T20:42:23.292000000",
  "caseindex": 74792,
  "workflowindex": 0,
  "name": "OfferState_1094188737",
  "action": "statechange",
  "starttime": "2016-02-24T20:42:23.292000000",
  "class": "Offer"
}
```

e2

```
{
  "activity": "O_Cancelled",
  "applicationindex": 0,
  "completetime": "2016-03-26T08:13:25.520000000",
  "caseindex": 74797,
  "workflowindex": 0,
  "name": "OfferState_1461884792",
  "action": "statechange",
  "starttime": "2016-03-26T08:13:25.520000000",
  "class": "Offer"
}
```

Started streaming 20898 records after 1 ms and completed after 4609 ms, displaying first 1000 rows.

(a)

Events	84,844
Cases	20,898
Activities	6
Median case duration	30.5 d
Mean case duration	23.8 d
Start	02.01.2016 10:17:05
End	01.02.2017 11:15:04

(b)

Figure C.11: Question 11 Screenshots

```
$ MATCH (c:Case) WITH c.variant as variant, count(*) AS count ORDER BY count DESC LIMIT 1 MATCH (c:Case) WHERE c.variant = variant RETURN c.name, variant, count
```

c.name	variant	count
"Application_889180637"	"Variant_7"	3
"Application_1065734594"	"Variant_7"	3
"Application_1076724533"	"Variant_7"	3

(a)

(b)

Figure C.12: Question 12 Screenshots

```
$ MATCH (c:Case) <-[:EVENT_TO_CASE]- (e:Event) <-[:DF*]- (e2:Event) WHERE NOT (c)-[:DF]- (e) AND NOT (e2)-[:DF]- (c) AND c.name = 'Application_681547497' RETURN (e, c)
```


(a)

(b)

Figure C.13: Question 13 Screenshots

(a)

(b)

Figure C.14: Question 14 Screenshots

\$ MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:DF]-

"from"	"to"	"frequency"
{"name":"User_1"}	{"name":"User_1"}	40
{"name":"User_28"}	{"name":"User_28"}	14
{"name":"User_49"}	{"name":"User_49"}	12
{"name":"User_61"}	{"name":"User_61"}	11
{"name":"User_78"}	{"name":"User_78"}	9
{"name":"User_121"}	{"name":"User_121"}	8
{"name":"User_40"}	{"name":"User_40"}	8
{"name":"User_75"}	{"name":"User_75"}	8
{"name":"User_5"}	{"name":"User_5"}	7
{"name":"User_7"}	{"name":"User_7"}	6
{"name":"User_123"}	{"name":"User_123"}	6
{"name":"User_24"}	{"name":"User_24"}	6

Figure C.15: Question 14 Frequency Screenshot

(a)

(b)

Figure C.16: Question 15 Screenshots

```
$ MATCH (r1:Resource) -[:RESOURCE_TO_EVENT]-> (e1:Event) <-[:O_DF]-
```

	"from"	"to"	"frequency"
	{"name": "User_28"}	{"name": "User_28"}	6
	{"name": "User_61"}	{"name": "User_61"}	4
	{"name": "User_5"}	{"name": "User_5"}	4
	{"name": "User_78"}	{"name": "User_78"}	4
	{"name": "User_49"}	{"name": "User_49"}	4
	{"name": "User_17"}	{"name": "User_17"}	3
	{"name": "User_21"}	{"name": "User_21"}	2
	{"name": "User_78"}	{"name": "User_1"}	2
	{"name": "User_7"}	{"name": "User_7"}	2
	{"name": "User_85"}	{"name": "User_85"}	2
	{"name": "User_56"}	{"name": "User_56"}	2
	{"name": "User_52"}	{"name": "User_52"}	2

Figure C.17: Question 15 Frequency Screenshot

(a)

Case ID	Events	Variant	Started	Finished	▲ Duration
Offer_2140369778	8	Varia...	28.10.2016 17:58:48	22.11.2016 08:42:13	24 days, 15 hours
Offer_1845937308	8	Varia...	29.11.2016 14:33:27	23.12.2016 14:59:55	24 days, 26 mins
Offer_713767690	7	Varia...	25.10.2016 10:34:13	11.11.2016 08:33:33	16 days, 22 hours
Offer_116103364	8	Varia...	02.05.2016 11:00:01	18.05.2016 14:11:05	16 days, 3 hours
Offer_1416171205	7	Varia...	21.07.2016 14:43:04	03.08.2016 16:44:55	13 days, 2 hours
Offer_2117778229	5	Varia...	30.06.2016 15:30:21	13.07.2016 09:43:32	12 days, 18 hours
Offer_228906169	6	Varia...	16.11.2016 19:16:06	28.11.2016 12:54:42	11 days, 17 hours
Offer_658074264	5	Varia...	08.06.2016 16:48:14	20.06.2016 09:22:41	11 days, 16 hours
Offer_473389986	7	Varia...	17.06.2016 14:56:23	28.06.2016 14:23:02	10 days, 23 hours
Offer_2024854898	6	Varia...	27.07.2016 10:12:34	05.08.2016 09:18:51	8 days, 23 hours
Offer_110013904	7	Varia...	22.04.2016 16:40:36	29.04.2016 16:08:15	6 days, 23 hours
Offer_1982741376	6	Varia...	24.03.2016 19:11:53	31.03.2016 17:13:48	6 days, 21 hours
Offer_104557954	6	Varia...	17.03.2016 19:19:41	24.03.2016 10:11:01	6 days, 14 hours
Offer_695278225	4	Varia...	10.11.2016 10:06:38	10.11.2016 14:48:07	4 hours, 41 mins
Offer_525000000	2	Varia...	10.11.2016 17:00:00	10.11.2016 17:00:00	0 mins, 00 secs

(b)

Figure C.18: Question 16 Screenshots

length(p)

(:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (end)

20

[[

```
{
  "name": "Offer_116103364",
  "offeredamount": "22500.0",
  "monthlycost": "442.16",
  "n_terms": "57",
  "firstamount": "2000.0",
  "creditscore": "740"
}
```

(a)

	Activity	Resource	FirstWithdrawalAmount	NumberOfTerms	Accepted	OfferID
1	A_Create Application	User_1				
2	A_Submitted	User_1				
3	A_Concept	User_1				
4	W_Complete application	User_40				
5	A_Accepted	User_28				
6	O_Create Offer	User_28	2000.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
7	O_Created	User_28	2000.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
8	O_Create Offer	User_28	4500.0	57	true	Offer_1637882280
9	O_Created	User_28	4500.0	57	true	Offer_1637882280
10	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_28	4500.0	57	true	Offer_1637882280
11	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_28	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
12	W_Call after offers	User_28	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
13	A_Complete	User_28	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
14	W_Validate application	User_29	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
15	A_Validating	User_2	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
16	O_Returned	User_2	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
17	W_Call incomplete files	User_29	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
18	A_Incomplete	User_29	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
19	W_Validate application	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
20	A_Validating	User_120	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
21	W_Call incomplete files	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
22	A_Incomplete	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
23	W_Validate application	User_118	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
24	A_Validating	User_118	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
25	W_Call incomplete files	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
26	A_Incomplete	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
27	O_Accepted	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
28	A_Pending	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_116103364
29	O_Cancelled	User_75	4500.0	57	true	Offer_1637882280

(b)

Figure C.19: Question 17 Screenshots

length(p) 3

(:Offer) <-[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]- (end)

```
{
  "name": "Offer_2024854898",
  "offeredamount": "25000.0",
  "monthlycost": "250.0",
  "n_terms": "126",
  "firstamount": "0.0",
  "creditscore": "0"
}
```

(a)

	Activity	Resource	FirstWithdrawalAmount	NumberOfTerms	Accepted	OfferID	M
1	A_Create Application	User_35					
2	A_Concept	User_35					
3	W_Complete application	User_35					
4	A_Accepted	User_21					
5	O_Create Offer	User_21	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
6	O_Created	User_21	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
7	O_Sent (mail and online)	User_21	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
8	W_Call after offers	User_21	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
9	A_Complete	User_21	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
10	W_Validate application	User_27	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
11	A_Validating	User_27	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
12	O_Returned	User_27	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
13	O_Accepted	User_30	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2
14	A_Pending	User_30	0.0	126	true	Offer_2024854898	2

(b)

Figure C.20: Question 18 Screenshots

C.2 Question 19 Evaluation

C.2.1 Python Script

```
1 import pandas as pd
2 from py2neo import Graph
3 import time
4
5 loan_raw = pd.read_csv('bpiChallenge17.csv', keep_default_na=False) #load full log
6   from csv
7 loan_raw.drop_duplicates(keep='first', inplace=True) #remove duplicates from the
8   dataset
9 loan_raw = loan_raw.reset_index(drop=True) #renew the index to close gaps of
10  removed duplicates
11
12 file = 'BPIC17_clean.csv'
13 loan_raw.to_csv(file, index=False)
```

```

12 sampleIds = loan_raw.case.unique().tolist() # create a list of all cases in the
    dataset
13 noOfCases = len(cases)
14
15 start = time.time() ##### start csv analysis
16 print('Start CSV analysis...')
17
18 log = []
19 #for id in sampleIds:
20 for case in sampleIds:
21     offerIds = [] # list to keep track of offerIDs within a case
22     offerSequences = [] #list of activity-sequences for offers to the corresponding
        offerIds variable: offerIds[0] refers to offerSequences[0], etc.
23     caseSequence = [] #list of activity-sequences for the case
24     i = 0 #variable used for temp indices
25     j = 0 #variable used for temp indices
26     matchCount = 0 # count the "hits" - i.e. a hit = one offer where O_Created is
        directly followed by O_Cancelled of the same offer.
27
28     for index, row in loan_raw[loan_raw.case == case].iterrows():
29         rowList = list(row)
30         if (row['EventOrigin']=="Offer" and row['event'] != "O_Create Offer"): #
            only execute if event is an offer event except O_Create Offer
31             if (row['OfferID'] in offerIds): #if offerID has been observed before
32                 i = offerIds.index(row['OfferID']) #get index of that offerID
33                 offerSequences[i].append(row['event']) #add the activity to the
                sequence of the offer
34             else:
35                 offerIds.append(row['OfferID']) #add offerID to id list
36                 i = offerIds.index(row['OfferID']) #get index of that offerID
37                 offerSequences.append([row['event']]) #add the activity to the
                sequence of the offer
38                 caseSequence.append(rowList) #add the complete event information (row) to
                case sequence list
39
40     offerMatches = [False for i in range(len(offerIds))]
41     for sequence in offerSequences:
42         for activity in sequence:
43             if (activity == 'O_Cancelled' and len(sequence) > 1): #if current event
                is not the first of the sequence and activity is = O_Cancelled
44                 i = sequence.index(activity) #get the current activity index in the
                sequence list
45                 if (sequence[i-1] == 'O_Created'): #if the preceding activity
46                     matchCount += 1 #count as hit
47                     offerMatches[j] = True #mark as match
48             j += 1
49
50     if(matchCount > 1):
51         log.append([caseSequence, offerIds, offerSequences, offerMatches]) #add case,
            offerids+sequences+boolean if an offer is a "match" to new "log" if case has at
            least 2 hits
52
53 header = ['CaseSequence', 'OfferIds', 'OfferSequences', 'OfferMatches']
54 LogDf = pd.DataFrame(log, columns=header) #create pandas dataframe
55 #now we have identified all cases that meet the requirements of >= 2 offers with
        O_Created directly followed by O_Cancelled (with ALL their offers)
56
57 finalLog = [] #will contain a list for each offer with caseID, offerID and the
        sequence from start to the case till O_Cancelled of that offer
58 for i in LogDf.index: #for every object in the data frame
59     caseId = LogDf.iloc[i]['CaseSequence'][0][0] #get caseID
60     for offerId in LogDf.iloc[i]['OfferIds']: #iterate through offerID list
61         index = LogDf.iloc[i]['OfferIds'].index(offerId)

```

```

62     tSequence = [] #the "target" sequence per offer (A_Create Application to
        O_Created)
63     if (LogDf.iloc[i]['OfferMatches'][index] == True): #only do for matching
        offers
64         for activity in LogDf.iloc[i]['CaseSequence']:
65             tSequence.append(activity[1]) #keep adding activities to that
        offers' sequence
66             if (activity[1] == "O_Cancelled" and activity[11] == offerId): #
        until O_Cancelled of that offer is added
67                 break
68             finalLog.append([caseId, offerId, tSequence]) # add that offers' sequence
        to the final log
69
70 header = ['CaseID', 'OfferID', 'OfferSequence']
71 LogDfCSV = pd.DataFrame(finalLog, columns=header) #create pandas dataframe (for
        stats only)
72 print(str(len(LogDfCSV.CaseID.unique())) + ' Cases with ' + str(len(LogDfCSV)) + '
        Offers have been identified.')
73 end = time.time() #end csv analysis
74
75 print("The analysis of the CSV file took "+str((end - start))+ " seconds to complete
        .")
76
77 start = time.time() #start graph analysis
78 print('Start Graph analysis...')
79
80 graph = Graph(password="1234") #connect to local Neo4j DB with password
81
82 #define the query
83 query = """
84 MATCH (e1:Event { activity: "O_Created"})<-[O_DF]-(e2:Event { activity: "
        O_Cancelled"}) -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o: Offer) -[:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c:Case)
85 WITH c AS c, count(o) AS ct
86 WHERE ct > 1
87 MATCH (:Event { activity: "O_Created"})<-[O_DF]-(e:Event { activity: "O_Cancelled"})
        -[:EVENT_TO_OFFER]-> (o: Offer) -[:OFFER_TO_CASE]-> (c)
88 WITH c AS c, o AS o, e AS O_Cancelled
89 MATCH p = (A_Create:Event { activity: "A_Create Application"}) <-[DF*]-
        (O_Cancelled:Event { activity: "O_Cancelled"}), (O_Cancelled) -[:EVENT_TO_CASE]->
        (c)
90 RETURN p,c
91 """
92
93 data = graph.run(query) #run query on Neo4j DB
94
95 output = pd.DataFrame([list(x) for x in data]) #save the output to pandas dataframe
96 finalLogGraph = [] #
97 for index, p in output.iterrows():
98     path = []
99     offerId = output[0][index].nodes[-1]['offerid'] #get offerID from the current
        traces' last node (every trace consists of activities from A_Create Application
        to O_Cancelled)
100    caseId = output[1][index]['name'] #get caseID, match/return of the case in the
        query has been included to verify the case->offer->activity sequence
101    for node in output[0][index].nodes: #walk over the nodes
102        path.append(node['activity'])#and add the activities in their order to a
        list
103    finalLogGraph.append([caseId, offerId, path]) #add caseid, offerid and sequence to
        list to have the data in the same output data format as the csv analysis
104
105 header = ['CaseID', 'OfferID', 'OfferSequence']
106 LogDfG = pd.DataFrame(finalLogGraph, columns=header) #create pandas dataframe (for
        stats only)

```

```

107 print(str(len(LogDfG.CaseID.unique())) + ' Cases with ' + str(len(LogDfG)) + '
    Offers have been identified.')
108
109 end = time.time() #end Graph analysis
110
111 print("The analysis of the graph query took "+str((end - start))+ " seconds to
    complete.")
112
113 print('Comparing results...')
114 if (sorted(finalLog) == sorted(finalLogGraph)): #check if (sorted list) results are
    equal
115     print('The results match')
116 else:
117     print('The results do NOT match')

```

C.2.2 Output

```

Start CSV analysis...
103 Cases with 218 Offers have been identified.
The analysis of the CSV file took 927.1300814151764 seconds to complete.
Start Graph analysis...
103 Cases with 218 Offers have been identified.
The analysis of the graph query took 0.9635610580444336 seconds to complete.
Comparing results...
The results match

```

Figure C.21: Output of the Q19 Python Script

C.2.3 Execution Times on Full Graph

Question	Execution Time in seconds
1	case
2	event
3	startTime
4	completeTime
5	LoanGoal
6	ApplicationType
7	RequestedAmount
8	Accepted
9	Action
10	FirstWithdrawalAmount
11	NumberOfTerms
12	OfferID

Table C.1: Query Execution Times

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